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¹ *PU* Public
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RE Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)
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1.2	30.01.2022	Danuta Frydryszak	Some SOPs corrected after adjusting the methods during the experiments
1.3	20.01.2023	Ryszard Laskowski	Description of the methods unified
2.0	03.03.2023	Ryszard Laskowski	The manuscript standardized to the format required for EcoStack deliverables
2.1	08.03.2023	Ryszard Laskowski	Minor corrections. The final version of the deliverable reviewed and accepted by all authors

1 Honeybee (*Apis mellifera*) – acute oral toxicity test

Standard Operation Procedure (SOP) reference number: CFE-UC-12

1.1 Objective

The objective of this SOP is to assess the acute toxicity of pesticides and other chemicals to adult worker honeybees exposed by oral administration.

1.2 Principle of the test

The purpose of this test is to expose adult honeybees to different dosages of a toxic substance via a contaminated diet (sucrose solution). It has a minimum duration of 48 hours with mortality values being registered at each of the defined time points (4-6, 24 and 48 hours). In case the mortality rate of bees exposed to the test substance increases between 24 and 48h but control mortality (same diet without the test substance) remains at an accepted level, i.e. $\leq 10\%$, it is advised to extend the test to a maximum of 96h. The LD₅₀ is calculated for 24 and 48h (in case the test is extended, LD₅₀ is also calculated for 72 and 96h).

1.3 Description of the method

1.3.1 Specimen selection and husbandry

- The selection of the bees should be performed from adequately fed and disease-free, non-sister colonies;
- Young adult worker bees, with identical characteristics (race, age, feeding status, ...), should be collected from frames without brood, early in the morning of use or, if collected in the evening, bees should be allowed to acclimate to test conditions until the next day;
- Early spring and late autumn bee's collection should be avoided due to variation in specimen physiology. In case tests need to be performed during these times of the year, bees can be emerged in an incubator and reared for one week with "bee bread" (pollen collected from the comb) and sucrose solution;
- In case any chemical treatment is applied in the colonies, the correspondent bees should not be used for four weeks from the time of the last treatment;

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² SOP based on OECD guideline 213 [1] and on EPPO Guideline for evaluating side effects of plant protection products on honeybees (*Apis mellifera*) [2].

1.4 Preparation for the test

1.4.1 Bee handling and test cages

- Single-use test cages (used once and discarded) should be employed in order to minimize contamination by pathogens and chemical residues (difficult to remove completely) between experiments (Williams et al., 2013).
- Cages should fulfil the following minimum criteria:
 - inexpensive, easily accessible and made of material easy to manipulate (e.g. plastic) that allows modifications of the cages;
 - well-ventilated (with sufficient air holes);
 - with at least one transparent surface that allows observation;
 - allow easy removal of alive and dead bees during experiment while not allowing accidental escapes;
 - support feeding devices that do not require opening cages for replacement.
- Each test cage should contain 10 bees. The test cages should provide adequate space for 10 bees ($\geq 200 \text{ cm}^3$; Williams et al., 2013) (Figure 1). At the bottom of each cage a filter paper can be placed which facilitates cleaning when there is a leakage and prevents bees from getting soaked. The filter paper should be replaced (through a small incision in the lower part of the cage) whenever needed (e.g. if signs of food leakage or abnormal events like diarrhea are observed).
- Both the placement of the collected bees in cages and of these cages in the experimental room should be done randomly. Before the beginning of the test bees have to be starved for up to 2h. In case dying bees are observed by the end of this period, they should be replaced with healthy specimens.
- A sucrose solution in water of 500 g/l (50% w/v) can be used as food and must be given *ad libitum* after the initial feeding with the treatment doses (see section 5.3). Feeders must fulfil the following minimum criteria:
 - Allow workers to drink safely without drowning;
 - Hold the respective volume securely, minimize evaporation, and prevent leakage;
 - Ensure feeding sites are not easily blocked by crystallization;

- Allow for quick and easy replenishment of the solution, as well as measurement of consumption, which consequently minimizes accidental escape of experimental individuals (Williams et al., 2013).
- Two simple disposable types of feeders can be made using microcentrifuge tubes (≤ 2 ml). A vertical (positioned on the top/lid of the cage) with three small holes 0.5-1 mm wide drilled along the microtube (by using a syringe needle). Alternatively, a lateral (positioned on the side surfaces/walls) feeding device can be created by drilling a single 5-7 mm wide hole on one side of the microtube.
- Bee's manipulation and observation can be done under light conditions.

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Figure 1. An example of a test cage and its dimensions (suitable for housing 10 bees).

1.4.2 Doses:

- Stock and feeding solutions for each treatment (controls and test chemical) are prepared with 50% (w/v) aqueous sucrose solution (preferably using deionized water). In case of low water solubility of a pesticide, an organic solvent such as acetone, dimethylformamide or dimethylsulfoxide can be used. The concentration of this solvent should not exceed 1%.
- If the usage of an organic solvent is needed, 2 different control batches should be adopted: a sucrose solution in water and a sucrose solution with the solvent (concentration used in dosing solutions).

1.5 Procedure

1.5.1 Test and control groups

- At least 5 doses in a geometric series, with a factor not exceeding 2.2, covering the LD₅₀ are needed for the test. The dilution factor and the number of concentrations for dosage are determined in relation to the slope of the dose-response toxicity curve. A range-finding test can be done to better find the appropriate test doses;
- Three replicates (cages) with 10 bees each (total of 30) are required per treatment: control, positive control, solvent control (when applicable), and the different concentrations of the tested chemical.

1.5.2 Toxic standard / Positive control

At least 3 doses of the toxic standard should be selected to cover the LD₅₀. For each dose, 3 replicates should be used, each replicate containing 10 bees. Dimethoate is the chemical of preference for which the reported LD₅₀ for the 24h after the administration is in the range 0.10-0.35 µg a.i./bee [3-4]. Nonetheless other toxic standards can be used if provided with enough data.

1.5.3 Doses administration

- Each test group (replicate) should be provided with 100-200 µl of 50% sucrose solution in water containing the test substance (larger volumes can be used if test substance is of low solubility, low toxicity, etc.). The amount of treated diet consumed per replicate should be recorded on, e.g., a weight basis;
- Remove the feeder after the solution consumption (3-4 hours) and introduce a feeder with only sucrose solution, that from this point on should be provided ad libitum;
- In case a clear rejection of the solution with the test substance occurs after 6h (e.g. cases of high concentration), the solution should be replaced with a sucrose solution only. Also in these cases, the amount of treated diet consumed should be assessed (e.g. measurement of volume/weight of treated diet remaining).

1.5.4 Test conditions, duration and observations

- Bees should be kept under dark in a temperature and humidity-controlled room (temperature: 25° ±2°C; humidity 50-70%);

- After the replacement of the test solution with the sucrose solution alone, the test has a duration of 48h with the possibility to be extended up to 96h (if mortality is increasing by more than 10% while the control remains under 10%);
- Mortality is recorded at 4h after the start of the test and thereafter 24h and 48h (72h and 96h in case the test is extended);
- When the diet is rejected by the bees and no consumption is observed, instead of replacing it with the sucrose solution after 3-4 hours, the diet should remain at the cage for a maximum of 6 hours and then replaced with an untreated sucrose solution;
- All abnormal behavioral effects observed during the testing period should be recorded.

1.6 Validity of the test

In order for a test to be considered valid:

- the average mortality of the total number of controls must be less than 10%;
- the LD₅₀ of the reference substance should be within specified limits.

1.7 Data analysis

Data should be summarized in a tabular form, displaying each treatment, control(s) and toxic standard groups. Information on the number of bees used, mortality rate and abnormal behavior should be collected and reported.

Probit analysis, moving-average, binomial probability are some of the appropriate methods to use when analyzing mortality. For each observation time, the slopes of the dose-response curve and the median lethal doses should be calculated [5].

In case the diet is not completely ingested, the LD₅₀ for the consumed amount of test substance should be calculated and expressed in µg per bee.

1.8 Report

The final report should include:

- physical nature, relevant physical-chemical properties, chemical identification data, structural formula and purity of the test substance;
- relevant information on the species/specimens used (scientific name, age, date and method of collection, ...) and respective colonies (health, treatments, ...);
- room temperature and humidity during the experiment;
- type, size and material of the cages;

- preparation of stock and test solutions;
- number and test concentrations used, number of controls, number of replicate cages and number of bees per cage.

1.9 Limit test

When the test substance is expected to be of low toxicity or low solubility, a limit test may be performed using 100µg a.i. /bee, or the maximum achievable solubility if it's a poorly soluble substance (whichever is lower is the one to be performed), in order to show that no effects are observed at this concentration of the substance. Limit test is performed for each replicate, with a minimum of 10 adult bees per replicate (3 x 10 = 30 total). Control test(s) should be performed as well. In case of statistically significant effects are observed by the end of the limit test when compared with the control, a complete study should be performed.

1.10 Bibliography

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2 Honeybee (*Apis mellifera*) – acute contact toxicity test

Standard Operation Procedure (SOP) reference number: CFE-UC-2³

2.1 Objective

The objective of this SOP is to assess the acute contact toxicity of pesticides and other chemicals, to adult worker honeybees.

2.2 Principle of the test

The purpose of this test is to assess the effect of different dosages of a chemical on adult honeybee mortality after direct application onto the thorax, for a minimum of 48 hours and compare the results to control mortality values (same exposure without the test substance). In case mortality rate from the test substance increases between 24 and 48h and control mortality remains at an accepted level, i.e. $\leq 10\%$, it is advised to extend the test to a maximum of 96h. The LD₅₀ is calculated for 24 and 48h (in case it is extended, LD₅₀ is calculated for 72 and 96h).

2.3 Description of the method

2.3.1 Specimen selection and husbandry

- The selection of the bees should be performed from 3 healthy, adequately fed and disease-free non-sisters colonies;
- Young adult worker bees, from frames without brood, should be selected for the test and the extraction needs to be done early in the morning or in the evening;
- Early spring and late autumn bee's extractions should be avoided due to a variation in specimen's physiology. In case tests need to be performed during that time of the year, bees can be emerged in an incubator and reared for one week with "bee bread" (pollen collected from the comb) and sucrose solution;
- In case of chemical treatment of the colonies, bees from those colonies should not be used for four weeks from the time of the treatment;

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³ SOP based on OECD guideline 214 [1] and on EPPO Guideline for evaluating side effects of plant protection products on honeybees (*Apis mellifera*) [2].

2.4 Preparation for the test

2.4.1 Bee handling and test cages

- Bees should be anaesthetized at 4°C for a couple of minutes (the ideal time should be assessed in prior tests) in order to enable the application of the test substance. In case any dying bees are observed, they should be replaced with healthy specimens before the beginning of the test.
- Test cages should be kept well-ventilated and should be easy to clean and can be made out of stainless steel, wire mesh, plastic, disposable wooden cages, etc. Each test cage should contain 10 bees. The size of test cages should be appropriate to the number of bees, i.e. providing adequate space.
- Bees can be treated and observed under light conditions. A sucrose solution in water of 500 g/l (50% w/v) can be used as food and must be given *ad libitum* during the test. A pierced conic shape plastic microtube of 2 ml will be used.

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Figure 2. An example of a test cage and its dimensions (suitable for housing 10 bees)..

2.4.2 Doses

- The test substance is to be applied as solution in a carrier, an organic solvent or a water solution with a wetting agent. Acetone is an organic solvent of preference, but other solvents of low toxicity can be used, such as dimethylformamide or dimethylsulfoxide. The percentage of the organic solvent used should not surpass 1% of the solution used. For water dispersed formulated products and highly polar organic substances not soluble in organic carrier solvents, solutions may be easier to apply if prepared in a weak solution of a commercial wetting agent (e.g. Agral, Citowett, Lubrol, Triton, Tween).

- Proper control groups should be used, treated with water, and in case of a solvent/dispersant usage, a separate control group should be treated with the solvent/dispersant.

2.5 Procedure

2.5.1 Test and control groups

- 5 doses in a geometric series, with a factor not exceeding 2.2, covering the LD₅₀ are needed for the test;
- The dilution factor and the number of concentrations for dosage are determined in relation to the slope of the dose-response toxicity curve. A range-finding test can be done to better find the appropriate test doses
- 3 different replicate test groups (10 bees each) are required for each concentration. Each replicate group within the same concentration must be from a different colony (the 3 colonies have individuals in each concentration tested);
- 3 control replicates (10 bees each) should be performed along with the test. Additional 3 replicates should be included in case of a solvent usage. The distribution of the bees from each colony per control treatment follows the same rule as above.

2.5.2 Toxic standard / Positive control

At least 5 doses of the toxic standard should be selected to cover the LD₅₀. For each dose, 3 replicates should be used, each replicate containing 10 bees. Dimethoate is the chemical of preference for which the reported LD₅₀ for the 24h after the administration is in the range 0.10-0.30 µg a.i./bee [3-4], however other toxic standards can be used if provided with enough data.

2.5.3 Doses administration

- Anaesthetized (using CO₂ or cold) bees are individually treated by topical application. The selection of the bees from each colony for different doses is performed randomly;
- 1 µl of solution containing the test substance should be applied with a microapplicator to the dorsal side of the thorax of each bee;
- Bees are then moved to test cages and administered ad libitum with sucrose solution.

2.5.4 Test conditions, duration and observations

- The bees should be kept under dark in a temperature and humidity-controlled room (temperature: $33^{\circ} \pm 2 \text{ C}^4$; humidity 50-70%);
- The test has its duration of 48h with the possibility to be extended up to 96h (in case the mortality is increasing by more than 10% while the control remains under 10%);
- Mortality is recorded at 4h after the start of the test and thereafter 24h and 48h (72h and 96h in case the test is extended).

2.6 Validity of the test

In order for a test to be considered valid:

- the average mortality of the total number of controls must be less than 10%;
- the LD_{50} of the reference substance should be within specified limits.

2.7 Data analysis

- Data should be summarized in a tabular form, displaying each treatment, control(s) and toxic standard groups. Information on the number of bees used, mortality rate, abnormal behavior should be collected and reported.
- Probit analysis, moving-average, binomial probability are some of the appropriate methods to use when analyzing mortality [5]. For each observation time, the slopes of the dose-response curve and the median lethal doses should be calculated.
- In case when the diet is not completely ingested, the LD_{50} for the consumed amount of test substance should be calculated and expressed in μg per bee.

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2.8 Report

The final report should include:

- physical nature and relevant physical-chemical properties;
- chemical identification data, structural formula, purity;
- any information on the species/specimens used;
- any information on the colonies used for bees collection;
- temperature and humidity during the experiment;

⁴ This temperature is advised for Southern European *Apis mellifera iberiensis*. In case of *Apis mellifera mellifera*, the temperature of 25°C should be used [5].

- type, size and material of the cages;
- preparation of stock and test solutions;
- number and test concentrations used, number of controls, number of replicate cages and number of bees per cage.

2.9 Limit test

When the test substance is expected to be of low toxicity or of low solubility, a limit test may be performed. Using 100 µg a.i./bee or the maximum achievable solubility if it's a poorly soluble substance (whichever is lower is the one to be performed), in order to show that no effects are observed at this concentration of the substance. Limit test is performed for each replicate (colony) with a minimum of 14 adult bees per replicate (3 x 14 = 42 total). Control test(s) should be performed as well. In case of statistically significant effects are observed by the end of the limit test when compared with the control, a complete study should be performed.

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3 Honeybee (*Apis mellifera*) – larval toxicity test

Standard Operation Procedure (SOP) reference number: CFE-UC-3⁵

3.1 Objective

The objective of this SOP is to assess lethal and sub-lethal (emergence) toxicity of pesticides and other chemicals, to honeybee larvae exposed to contaminated food.

3.2 Principle of the test

The purpose of this test is to assess the effects of different dosages of chemicals on honeybee larvae mortality and emergence. At the beginning of the test (D1), first instar larvae of the same age are selected from 3 different colonies, each one representing a replicate, and placed into a 48 well-plates. From D3 to D6, larvae will be provided with food mixed with the test substance. The test chemical is provided daily to the larvae at a constant concentration corresponding to increasing test chemical doses per larva per day with the diet resulting in a cumulative dose on day 6 (for each treatment level) in a range of at least five increasing test concentrations. The mortality rate and any abnormal behavior is recorded from D4 to D8, and afterwards recorded on D15. On D22 the emergence rate is observed and recorded. The NOEC/NOED and, if data allows, the EC₅₀/ED₅₀, and/or EC_x/ED_x, are determined for adult emergence on D22.

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3.3 Test chemical

3.3.1 Information on the test chemical

The following information on the test chemical should be available before the beginning of the test:

- Water and solvent solubility;
- Vapour pressure;
- Chemical identification data, structural formula, purity, stability in water and octanol-water partition coefficient (K_{ow});
- Physical appearance and source (batch and lot number).

⁵ SOP based on OECD guidelines 239 [1] and 237 [4].

3.3.2 Reference chemical (positive control)

The reference chemical is used to guarantee that the way the test is designed and its conditions are responsive and trustworthy at the constant concentration of the reference chemical.

Dimethoate or fenoxycarb can be used as reference chemicals, at constant concentrations of 48 mg active ingredient (a.i.)/Kg of diet (i.e. 0.053 µg a.i./µL of diet) and 0.320 mg a.i./Kg of diet (i.e. 0.35 ng a.i./µL of diet) respectively [3, 5]. The table below indicates the amount of dimethoate and fenoxycarb which has to be added to the diet every day for one larva during the exposure period from D3 to D6, in order to maintain a constant concentration of the reference chemical. Preliminary experiments with these substances can help to select the most appropriate reference chemical.

Table 1. Amount of a reference chemical added to the diet on each experimental day; from OECD Guidance Document on honeybee (*Apis mellifera*) Larval Toxicity Test, Repeated Exposure

Day	D3	D4	D5	D6	Total amount/larva
Amount of dimethoate (µg) added to the diet	1.06	1.58	2.11	2.64	7.39
Amount of fenoxycarb (ng) added to the diet	7.04	10.56	14.08	17.60	49.28

3.4 Preparation for the test

3.4.1 Preparation of the larvae:

- Select first instar larvae from 3 healthy, adequately fed and disease-free non-sister colonies, each colony representing a different replicate;
- Performing a pre-test with a considerable number of larvae from each colony, to check for potential signs of variability and test performance regarding each replicate is advised;
- In case of chemical treatment of the colonies, bees from those colonies should not be used for four weeks from the time of the treatment;
- Perform the test during the egg laying period of the queen. To guarantee a sufficient number of larvae by the time of the beginning of the test, 3 days before the test starts (D-3), the

queens are confined to an exclusion cage with an empty comb (inside their own colonies). The cage is set near brood combs;

- At D-2 (but no longer than 30 hours of encaging), if freshly laid eggs are observed, the queens are released from the cages (the isolation time of the queens should be reduced as much as possible in order to prevent an impactful variability in eggs ages);
- 4 days after the queen isolation (D1), the comb with the hatched larvae is transferred from the hive to the laboratory (temperature during the transportation should not drop below 20°C) inside of an insulated container;
- The comb is then transferred into a switched off laminar-flow hood for grafting;
- Newly hatched larvae are selected for the test.
- Larvae that have not formed a “C” shaped form and/or larvae lying in royal jelly are selected for the test;
- Larvae selection from each colony and placement into the plates should be as randomized as possible.

3.4.2 Apparatus

The experimental unit is the individual crystal polyester grafting cell containing a larva. Each cell has 9 mm diameter and a depth of 8mm (Figure 1). Using ethanol or other sterilizing solution, the cells are sterilized by emerging them into the sterilizing solution for 30min and then dried in a laminar-flow hood. The cells are afterwards placed into a 48-well plate. The top of the grafting cell is maintained at the level of the plate, by placing a piece of dental roll wetted with approximately 500 µL of the sterilising solution containing 15.5% weight/volume glycerol and 0.4% of MBC at the bottom of the wells (Figure 3). The plates are then moved into a hermetic plexiglass desiccator. Desiccators are afterwards placed inside of a ventilated incubator with the surrounding temperature of 34-35°C, which should be kept over the entire duration of the test. The humidity inside of the desiccator needs to be adequate for each stage of larval development:

- D1 to D8 – relative humidity of 95% ± 5%; it can be obtained by filling a dish with potassium sulfate (K₂SO₄) saturated solution;
- D8 (pre-pupae stage) – the plates are moved into a hermetic container with a relative humidity of 80% ± 5%; it can be obtained by filling a dish with a saturated NaCl solution. Dental rolls are removed from the wells, and the container is then placed into an incubator.

- D15 (pupae stage) – the plates are moved into an emergence box, e.g. a crystal polypropylene box (e.g. 11 x 15 x 12 cm), having an aerated cover. Emerged bees are fed ad libitum with a syrup/sucrose solution. The way the solution is administered to the bees, is up to the experimenter. Bird feeders, syringes or any other tool can be used. The plates are placed into an incubator with a relative humidity of 50-80%.

Figure 3. Larval cell in a well-plate; from OECD Guidance Document on honeybee (*Apis mellifera*) Larval Toxicity Test, Repeated Exposure

3.4.3 Larvae food preparation

Depending on the stage of the larval development, the food that is needed for the administration is separated into 3 different diets.

- Diet A (D1): 50% weight of fresh royal jelly + 50% weight of an aqueous solution containing 2% weight of yeast extract, 12% weight of glucose and 12% weight of fructose.
- Diet B (D3): 50% weight of fresh royal jelly + 50% weight of an aqueous solution containing 3% weight of yeast extract, 15% weight of glucose and 15% weight of fructose.
- Diet C (D4 to D6): 50% weight of fresh royal jelly + 50% weight of an aqueous solution containing 4% weight of yeast extract, 18% weight of glucose and 18% weight of fructose.

The diets A, B and C have a density of about 1.1 mg/ μ L (e.g., 20 μ L diet correspond to 22 mg diet). Sugar conglomerates should be completely dissolved before the mixing with the royal jelly. Royal jelly should be collected during the preceding 12 months. It is separated in 5g aliquots and stored in

a freezer at $\leq -10^{\circ}\text{C}$. Royal jelly can be acquired from commercial sources, but the testing facility is required to provide data showing that the mortality during the larval period does not exceed 15%. Freshly prepared diets can be stored in a fridge at $\leq +5^{\circ}\text{C}$ for the entire duration of the test. If prepared in advance, diets should be deep-frozen (between -18°C and -22°C) and then transferred to a fridge at $\leq +5^{\circ}\text{C}$ during the running of the test.

3.5 Procedure

3.5.1 Test and control groups

- A minimum of 12, maximum of 16 larvae from each of 3 colonies are selected for the control groups;
- A minimum of 14 larvae from each of 3 colonies are selected for the solvent control groups in case of an organic solvent is used;
- A minimum of 14 larvae from each of 3 colonies are selected for the test of the reference chemical;
- A minimum of 14 larvae from each of 3 colonies are selected for each treatment level. A minimum of 5 levels of treatment should be performed in a geometric series with a factor not exceeding 3. It should cover the NOEC/NOED or the $\text{EC}_{50}/\text{ED}_{50}$ or any EC_x/ED_x ;

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A total of 7 to 8 well-plates are used per test. The group of 14 larvae per colony and per treatment level is considered to be a replicate and should be properly identified on the microplate. The plates should be kept under dark conditions as long as the test is running at a surrounding temperature of $34\text{-}35^{\circ}\text{C}$. The humidity should be regulated according to the stage of the larvae development.

NOTE 1: The test may be initialized with larvae in excess, and on D3 any observed dead larvae can be replaced with live specimens.

NOTE 2: Temporary deviations in temperature are allowed, however temperature should not drop below 23°C or go above 40°C , and these deviations should not last, as far as possible, more than 30 minutes once every 24 hour.

3.5.2 Range-finding test

The NOEC/NOED or the $\text{EC}_{50}/\text{ED}_{50}$ range needs to be calculated by running a preliminary test. In this test, the chemical concentrations need to vary according to a geometrical ratio from 5 to 10. The information obtained from this test will also help to determine the mode of action of the chemical, allowing a more accurate selection of the reference chemical.

3.5.3 Limit test

When the test substance is expected to be of low toxicity or of low solubility, a limit test may be performed. Using 100µg a.i. or test chemical/larva or the maximum achievable solubility if it's a poorly soluble substance (whichever is lower is the one to be performed), in order to show that no effects are observed at low concentration of the substance. Limit test is performed for each replicate (colony) with a minimum of 14 larvae per replicate (3 x 14 = 42 larvae total). Control test(s) and the reference chemical test should as well be performed. In case of statistically significant effects are observed by the end of the limit test when compared with the control, a complete study should be performed.

3.5.4 Test solutions

- The test substance is usually dissolved in deionized water, but in case it has low water solubility, organic solvent such as acetone can be used. The volume of the organic solvent should not exceed 2% of the diet final volume;
- If the usage of an organic solvent is required, 2 different control groups should be created: a solution in water (control) and a solution with the solvent (solvent control) (concentration used in dosing solutions);
- Stock solutions should be prepared at each feeding day (not necessary if the stability of the test substance has been demonstrated in previous studies).
- If water is used to dissolve the test substance into the diet, the volume of the solution should not exceed 10% of the final volume (e.g., 2 µL of test solution for a final diet volume of 20 µL on D3). If an organic solvent is used to dissolve the test substance, the volume of the solution should not exceed 2% of the final volume (e.g., 0.4 µL of test solution for a final diet volume of 20 µL on D3).
- The overall composition of the diet as stated in section 4.3 should be observed, i.e., the total volume of water/solvent used for preparing the test chemical solution should be taken into account for diet preparation. The test solution should be mixed into the diet in a manner that will result in even distribution of the test chemical throughout the diet (e.g. using ultrasonic dispersion).
- A sample of the test solution used to prepare the diet with the highest and lowest concentrations should be stored in a freezer at $\leq -20^{\circ}\text{C}$ for a later analytical determination of

the actual concentration of the test substance (ideally this analysis is run on the solution before the mixing with the royal jelly, that can complicate the analysis).

3.5.5 Food and test chemical administration

Before the administration to the larvae, the diet needs to be warmed in the incubator. The grafting is done on a warming plate at 34-35°C. The micropipettes with disposable tips or a multi-stepper pipette are used to place the diet into the cells.

- D1 – 20 μ L of diet A is placed in each cell. The larva should be lying with the same side facing up as they were in the wax cells, since they breathe from the spiracles located on the upper side of their body (Crailsheim et al., 2013; Schmehl et al., 2016). After the grafting of 8 larvae, the paintbrush should be disinfected in alcohol and washed in autoclaved water. When a plate is completed, with 16 larvae from each colony, it is placed, as far as possible and in a single layer, into the desiccator, which has previously been placed in the ventilated incubator. Grafting should not take longer than 20 minutes per 48 larvae and a warm and humid environment should be maintained throughout (Crailsheim et al., 2013; Schmehl et al., 2016);
- Every day, except on D2, all larvae are fed with the diet volume adapted for each stage/day of the test (see Figure 4);
- Extra care should be taken to avoid touching or drowning the larvae during the feeding procedure;
- Even if food is observed in the cell when administering a new dose, the new dose should be administered fully;
- On D8, any uneaten food should be recorded.

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The stock solution is mixed with the diets right before the food administration (unless the chemical stability has been demonstrated and reported).

- D3 – larvae are fed with diet B along with the test substance at suitable concentration;
- D4 to D6 – larvae are fed with diet C with the test substance at suitable concentrations.
- D15 to D22 – larvae are fed ad libitum with syrup and pollen solution.

Figure 4. Schematic representation of the test procedures; from OECD Guidance Document on honeybee (*Apis mellifera*) Larval Toxicity Test, Repeated Exposure

3.5.6 Termination of the test

The test is ended on D22, the number of emerged and non-emerged bees are counted, and the plates are frozen at $\leq -10^{\circ}\text{C}$ (or $\leq -80^{\circ}\text{C}$).

Bee mortality, if observed, must be recorded from D4 to D8 when feeding and then on D15. For larvae, an immobile larva, a larva that does not respond to physical contact of the grafting tool or paintbrush, or a larva that does not show any signs of respiration under a stereomicroscope is considered as dead and removed.

On D15, if a larva did not transform into pupae, it is considered as dead and removed.

On D22 normally developed adult bees that have left their cells (alive bees and dead bees that have successfully left their cells) are recorded. The emergence rate is calculated as percentage by comparing the number of emerged bees at D22 with the number of larvae at D3. The pupal mortality is calculated as percentage by comparing the number of pupae that failed to emerge from D8-D22 (including those bees without emergence on D22 and dead pupae removed during pupa stage – from D8 to D22) with the number of bees entering the pre-pupa stage on D8. The larvae mortality is calculated by comparing the number of dead larvae from D3 to D8 with the number of larvae at D3.

Any larval appearance, size, behavior, morphological differences, or any other relevant observation when comparing with control individuals, should be recorded qualitatively. In case of emerged bees showing any signs of a severe pain, they should be immediately euthanized by the most humane method.

3.6 Validity of the test

In order for a test to be considered valid:

- The cumulative mortality across all replicates of the control group from day D3 to D8 is expected to be $\leq 15\%$;
- On D22, the emergence of adult honeybees across all replicates of the control group is expected to be $\geq 70\%$;
- In case of dimethoate usage, on D8 the mortality observed across all replicates on positive control should be $\geq 50\%$;
- In case of fenoxycarb usage, on D22 the emergence rate observed across all replicates on positive controls should be $\leq 20\%$.

3.7 Data analysis

Data should be summarized in a tabular form, where the number of larvae used, mortalities and adverse effects can be clearly observed. This information should be collected for each treatment group, each control and chemical groups. For data analysis a suitable method should be used [6].

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3.7.1 NOEC/NOED estimation

On D22 the NOEC/NOED is determined for adult emergence. In case no effects are observed for any test concentrations, the NOEC/NOED is considered to be higher or equal to the highest concentration used in the test.

3.7.2 EC₅₀/ED₅₀/EC_x/ED_x estimation

If possible, an EC₅₀/ED₅₀ and any EC_x/ED_x, including the associated lower and upper confidence limits should be calculated for emerged adult bees on D22.

3.8 Report

The final report should include:

- Physical nature and relevant physical-chemical properties;
- Chemical identification data, structural formula, purity;
- Any information on the species/specimens used;

- Any information on the colonies used for bees collection;
- Temperature and humidity during the experiment;
- Preparation of stock and test solutions;
- Type of well-plates, information on the components of the diet, solvent and its concentrations, test chemical concentrations;
- Mortality rates at each treatment levels, controls and reference chemical;
- The nominal test concentrations used and measured concentration in the stock solution (should be within 20% of nominal).
- NOEC/NOED and/or EC50/ED50 and/or ECx/EDx for adult emergence on D22 and a graph of the fitted model, the slope of the concentration-response curve and its 95% confidence limits and the criteria for goodness of fit. Statistical procedures used to determine the NOEC/NOED and EC50/ECX;
- Any uneaten food observed on D8;

Any deviations from the test methodology, and how it affects the test results.

3.9 Bibliography

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4 Honeybee (*Apis mellifera*) – chronic oral toxicity test

Standard Operation Procedure (SOP) reference number: CFE-UC-4⁶

4.1 Objective

The objective of this SOP is to assess the chronic toxicity of pesticides and other chemicals, to young honeybees exposed to contaminated food.

4.2 Principle of the test

The purpose of this test is to expose recently emerged adult workers, maximum two days old, to different dosages of a toxic substance via a contaminated diet (sucrose), for a period of 10 days and compare the mortality and behavior abnormality data to control data (same diet without the test substance). The parameters to be derived after 10 days are the LC₅₀, LDD₅₀ (median Lethal Dietary Dose), NOEC and NOEDD (No Observed Effect Dietary Dose).

4.3 Description of the method

4.3.1 Specimen selection and husbandry

- The selection of the bees should be performed from 3 healthy, adequately fed and disease-free, non-sister colonies, each colony representing a replicate;
- Young bees (max. 2 days old) reared from brood combs should be selected for the test;
- In case of chemical treatment of the colonies, bees from those colonies should not be used for four weeks from the time of the treatment;
- Frames containing enough capped brood, capable of fulfilling the required number of adults for the test within a period of one to three days (with signs of emergence, e.g. small perforations in the wax capping of the brood cells, or pupae with dark eyes and cuticle), and few food stores should be selected (Human et al., 2013). All adult bees must be removed from the frame, using a brush or by gently shaking the frame over the colony, before placing it in an appropriate cage (Williams et al., 2013). The frame cage should be transferred to a laboratory incubator, where it will be maintained at constant conditions, and monitored frequently for newly emerged workers;

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⁶ SOP based on OECD guideline 245 [1] and on EPPO Guideline for evaluating side effects of plant protection products on honeybees (*Apis mellifera*) [2].

- The collection of the bees should be done one day before the starting of the test;
- During the collection, anesthetization of the bees should be avoided;
- Acclimatization to the test conditions is done over a period of one day (after a hatching period of one day); during this period, food (sucrose solution) should be given *ad libitum*, but no additional feeding of pollen or water is necessary during the acclimation and test period
- Single-use cages (used once and discarded) should be employed in order to minimize contamination by pathogens and chemical residues (difficult to remove completely) between experiments (Williams et al., 2013)
- Cages should fulfil the following minimum criteria:
 - inexpensive, easily accessible and manipulated material (e.g. plastic) that allows modifications of the cages;
 - well-ventilated (with sufficient air holes);
 - with at least one transparent surface that allows observation;
 - allow easy removal of alive and dead bees during experiment while not allowing accidental escapes;
 - support feeding devices that do not require opening cages for replacement;
 - provide adequate space for 10 bees (≥ 200 cm³) (Williams et al., 2013).
- At the bottom of each cage a filter paper can be placed which facilitates cleaning when there is a leakage and prevents bees from getting soaked. Filter paper should be replaced (through a small incision in the lower part of the cage) whenever needed (e.g. food leakage or abnormal events like diarrhea are observed);
- Feeding solution for the control, positive control, solvent control and test chemical are prepared with a 50% (w/v) aqueous sucrose solution. All solutions should be homogeneous and administered to the bees every day, with the interval of 24 h.

4.4 Preparation for the test

4.4.1 Bees

- Bees selected for the test from each colony should be randomly placed in the cages one day before the test starts (for acclimatization).

4.4.2 Doses

- Stock and feeding solutions for each treatment (controls and test chemical) are prepared with 50% (w/v) aqueous sucrose solution (preferably using deionized water). If a pesticide has low water solubility, organic solvent such as acetone can be used. The concentration of this solvent should not exceed 1%;
- If the usage of an organic solvent is needed, 2 different control batches should be used: a solution in water and a sucrose solution with the solvent (concentration used in dosing solutions);
- The stock solution can be prepared once for the entire test duration (depending on the stability of the test substance). After prepared, it should be stored in the dark in a tightly closed container ($6 \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$);
- In case the test solution has a quick degradation period, the stock solution should be prepared daily (or in an adequate time period);
- One aliquot of the lowest and one of the highest concentrations of the feeding solutions should be stored for analytical determination of the real concentration of the test substance in the feeding solution. In case the test solutions need to be prepared every day, the lowest and highest aliquots need to also be stored every day. Storage should be done at $\leq -18^{\circ}\text{C}$;
- Although stock solution can be prepared once for the entire duration of the experiment (10 days), the feeding solutions (test solution mixed with the sucrose solution) prepared based on the stock solution should have a maximum storage time of 4 days and should be kept at 6°C when not being used.

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4.5 Procedure

4.5.1 Test and control groups

- 5 doses in a geometric series, with a factor not exceeding 2.5 covering the LC_{50} and in order to determine the NOEC/NOEDD, the $\text{LD}_{50}/\text{LDD}_{50}$ with a 95% confidence limits;
- The dilution factor and the number of concentrations for dosage are determined in relation to the slope of the toxicity slope. A range-finding test can be done to better find the appropriate test doses;
- 3 different replicate test groups (20 bees each) are required for each concentration. Each replicate group within the same concentration must be from a different colony (the 3 colonies have individuals in each concentration tested);

- 3 control batches (20 bees each) should be performed along with the test. Additional 3 batches should be included in case of a solvent usage. The distribution of the bees from each colony per control treatment follows the same rule as above;
- 3 replicate groups should be used for the reference substance test. The distribution of the bees from each colony per control treatment follows the same rule as above.

4.5.2 Toxic standard / Positive control

At least 3 doses should be selected to cover the LD₅₀. For each dose, 3 replicates should be used, each replicate containing 20 bees. Dimethoate is the chemical of preference however another toxic standards can be used if provided with enough data. Concentration between 0.5 and 1.0 mg a.i./kg feeding solution is expected to obtain $\geq 50\%$ in mortality.

4.5.3 Doses administration

- Feeding devices (feeders) must fulfil the following minimum criteria:
- Allow workers to drink safely without drowning;
- Hold the respective volume securely, minimize evaporation, and prevent leakage;
- Ensure feeding sites are not easily blocked by crystallization;
- Allow for quick and easy replenishment of the solution, as well as measurement of consumption, which consequently minimizes accidental escape of experimental individuals (Williams et al., 2013).
- All feeding solutions should be homogeneous and at room temperature when administrated to the bees;
- Two simple disposable types of feeders can be made using microcentrifuge tubes (≤ 2 ml). A vertical (positioned on the top/lid of the cage) with three small holes 0,5-1 mm wide drilled along the microtube (by using a syringe needle). Alternatively, a lateral (positioned on the side surfaces/walls) feeding device can be created by drilling a single 5-7 mm wide hole on one side of the microtube;
- The feeding solutions are administered per replicate (bees are not fed individually). With food available to all the bees in the replicate cage, it is expected to all of the bees be exposed to the test substance;
- The feeding solutions are replaced/administered daily, by changing the feeders; feeding intervals of 24h;

- The weighing of the feeders before and after the feeding will allow calculating the amount of consumed feeding solution.

4.5.4 Evaporation

- To take into account possible evaporation, a feeding solution should be kept in the same conditions as in the rest of the experiment. 3 cages with no bees, containing at least 3 replicates each with the feeding solution. The feeding solution is replaced at the same time as the feeding solution administered to the bees, and weighed before and after its placement into the cages.
- The evaporation figure will be then subtracted from the values of the consumed food in order to obtain a real value for the consumed food.

4.5.5 Test conditions and duration

- The bees should be held in constant darkness (except during observation), in a temperature/humidity controlled room (temperature: $33^{\circ} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$; humidity 50% - 70%);
- Short-term deviations (≤ 2 hours per day) from the recommended test conditions are unavoidable and should not affect the integrity or outcome of the test;
- The duration of the test is of 10 days, during which bees are continuously exposed to the feeding solution;
- Mortality is recorded daily, preferably at the same time period (can be during the feeders replacement);
- Any abnormal behavior observed, should be noted (same time as mortality observations);
- Abnormal behavior should be classified as:

m = moribund (bees cannot walk and show only very feeble movements of legs and antennae, only weak response to stimulation; *e.g.* light or blowing; bees may recover but usually die);

a = affected (bees still upright and attempting to walk but showing signs of reduced coordination; hyperactivity; aggressiveness; increased self-cleaning behavior; rotations; shivering)

c = cramps (bees contracting abdomen or entire body),

ap = apathy (bees show only low or delayed reactions to stimulation *e.g.* light or puff of air; bees are sitting motionless in the unit).

v = vomiting.

- In case any other abnormal behavior is observed, it should be recorded and noted as clearly as possible;
- After the ending of the test, the test cages (with the bees inside) should be frozen at $\leq -10^{\circ}\text{C}$.

4.6 Validity of the test

In order for a test to be considered valid:

- the average mortality of across both the control and solvent control must be less than 15% (at the end of the experiment);
- the mortality rate of the reference substance group should be $\geq 50\%$ (at the end of the experiment).

4.7 Data analysis

- Data should be summarized in a tabular form, displaying each treatment, control(s) and toxic standard groups. Information on the number of bees used, mortality rate, abnormal behavior should be collected and reported;
- Probit analysis, moving-average, binomial probability are some of the appropriate methods to use when analyzing mortality and calculating the LC_{50} , the NOEC/NOEDD and the $\text{LD}_{50}/\text{LDD}_{50}$ with a 95% confidence limits [5];
- For the food consumption data, following calculations should be made:
 - mean consumption of feeding solution per bee for each day (mg/bee); the number of living bees at the beginning of each feeding interval is taken for this calculation;
 - overall mean daily consumption of feeding solution per treatment over the test period (mg/bee/day);
 - overall mean daily consumption of feeding solution per replicate over the test period (mg/bee/day);
 - mean uptake of test chemical per bee per day (μg or ng a.i./bee/day);
 - accumulated uptake of test chemical per bee over the test period (μg or ng a.i./bee);
 - when subtracting the “evaporation” value from the value of the consumed food, and it leads to a negative value, in this case the food consumption for that day is considered to be not existent.

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4.8 Report

The final report should include:

- physical nature and relevant physical-chemical properties;
- chemical identification data, structural formula, purity;
- any information on the species/specimens used;
- any information on the colonies used for bees collection;
- temperature and humidity during the experiment;
- type, size and material of the cages;
- preparation of stock and test solutions;
- number and test concentrations used, number of controls, number of replicate cages and number of bees per cage;
- all the data obtained and mentioned above.

4.9 Bibliography

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[5] OECD (2006). Current approaches in the statistical analysis of ecotoxicity data: a guidance to application. OECD Series on Testing and Assessment Number 54. (OECD, ENV/JM/MONO(2006)18), OECD, Paris:

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5 Red mason bee (*Osmia bicornis*) – determining the susceptibility to pesticides: contact test with individually exposed adults via topical exposure

SOP reference number: UJ-1 (Osmia adult topical test)

5.1 Objective

Determination of the effects of a single pesticide on topically exposed adult females of *Osmia bicornis* – individual exposure

5.2 Materials

5.2.1 Test substrate and food

- Test substrate: a pesticide solution in 0.1% Triton (a wetting agent)
- Food: Sucrose solution (33% by weight)

5.2.2 Test animals

- Species: *Osmia bicornis* females obtained from a controlled culture initiated from commercially available cocoons of *O. bicornis*. Upon arrival from the commercial supplier, the cocoons are stored in a fridge at 4°C until spring.
- Life stage: newly emerged females, i.e., those individuals which survived at least 96 h after emerging from the cocoon. 39

5.2.3 Test chemicals/stressors

- Pesticide of interest – a formulation or an active ingredient, depending on the goal of the test.

5.2.4 Climatic conditions

(P = Photoperiod: Light/Dark (h); T = Temperature (°C); RH = Relative Humidity (%) L = Light intensity (lux)

- Summer conditions: P: 16 L/8 D; T: 20°C; RH: 50%; L: 10000 – 20000 lux

5.2.5 Parameters measured

- Mortality

5.2.6 Other necessary materials/equipment

- Climatic chambers
- Standard laboratory equipment
- Paper boxes with holes for cocoons

- Transparent plastic boxes (e.g., 46x30x17 cm – length/width/height) with perforated lids (or covered with a mesh) for bees culturing after their emergence from cocoons
- Small plastic cups (ca. 500 ml) with perforated lids for individual housing after exposure or bigger transparent boxes (as above) for group housing
- Eppendorf tubes closed with cotton plugs or disposable plastic syringes (for sucrose solution to feed the bees)
- Hamilton micro-syringe (e.g., 30 µl) with automatic dispenser allowing precise application of 1 µl of a liquid

5.3 Experimental setup

Exposure to a pesticide topically (application of 1 µl of solution to the dorsal side of the thorax between the neck and wing base): at least four pesticide doses (treatment solutions prepared by diluting the test item with deionized water containing 0.1% Triton) and two controls (Triton 0.1 % and distilled water), each in 50 replicates (50 bees). The concentrations for tested pesticide, if not known, should be selected based on a range-finder study (*see below a short description for the range-finding experiment**).

5.4 Procedures

5.4.1 Prepare food for bees

Prepare 33% sucrose solution (33 g sucrose in 100 g distilled water).

Prepare at least 4 pesticide concentrations in 0.1% Triton solution and wrap the bottles with solutions with aluminum foil to avoid photodegradation. Store the solutions in a fridge (4°C) if not prepared on a day of exposure. Store samples of all pesticide solutions at -20°C for chemical analysis.

5.4.2 Emergence of *O. bicornis*

Transfer cocoons from 4°C to summer conditions. Select larger cocoons to be emerged to increase the fraction of females needed for the test (female cocoons are larger). Place ca. 100 cocoons per one cartoon box (ca. 10x10x5 cm).

Place the boxes with cocoons in bigger transparent plastic boxes (ca. 46x30x17 cm length/width/height) with perforated lids to allow air circulation. The bees emerging in cartoon boxes will move into light where they can be collected.

Control the boxes for emerged bees twice a day and immediately remove males if noticed (males usually emerge before females). Transfer the newly emerged females every day to a new breeding

box - place the newly emerged, meconium-free female bees in a new box of the same kind as the plastic emergence boxes but with a shelter for the bees (e.g., cardboard compartments from test-tube boxes) and a few Eppendorf tubes with sucrose solution (33%) closed with a cotton plug as a food source; attach an artificial yellow “flower” made of sponge to the Eppendorf. Optionally provide sucrose solution via disposable plastic syringes (e.g., 2 ml) with straight cropped tips and a yellow tape or sponge attached to its end simulating a flower.

Breed the bees *ad libitum* for 72 hours adding food when needed.

Use only healthy bees for the test.

5.4.3 Running the experiment

Prepare plastic test boxes (e.g., 500 ml cups) with perforated lids or covered with mesh and Eppendorf type 2 ml tube attached with a glue to the bottom of the cup. For individual exposure and housing prepare 300 boxes (4 treatments plus two controls (0.1% Triton and distilled water), each in 50 replicates (n=50 bees per treatment). Optionally, if group rather than individual housing of bees is planned, prepare six large transparent boxes (can be the same as the emergence boxes) with either disposable plastic syringes (e.g., 2 ml) attached to their walls a few Eppendorf tubes with sucrose solution (33%) closed with a cotton plug as a food source (4 pesticide treatments, 0.1% Triton and distilled water), one box per treatment, 50 individuals in each).

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Label each box with a proper number and treatment ID (pesticide name, pesticide dose, replicate) using a permanent marker.

Put sucrose solution into each Eppendorf tube and close the tubes with cotton plugs (or fill the syringes with sucrose solution); to allow better access to the solution attach a piece of yellow “flower” around the Eppendorf tube border (or around the cropped tip of the syringe) to increase visual attractiveness to bees and to allow easier access to food (landing place).

Inactivate females by keeping them no longer than for 30 minutes at 4°C, weigh them and transfer to a Petri dish, one bee per dish if individual exposure and housing is used. In case of individual exposure and group housing, weighing each bee separately before exposure is not needed as they are not followed individually anyway. In that case, place all bees per treatment in one dish and weigh them as a group to calculate average body mass.

Treat inactivated female bees individually by topical application of the test solution. Apply 1 µL of the treatment solution with a Hamilton micro-syringe with automatic dispenser to the dorsal side of the thorax between the neck and wing base.

After application, inactivate the bees again by putting glass dishes with bees in the polystyrene box filled with ice for approximately 5 min to ensure the infiltration of the treatment droplet.

Afterwards, transfer the bees to their cages (either individually or 50 bees per large box, depending on the experimental layout) and place test cages in the climatic chamber at summer conditions. Place the boxes with treated and control bees at random to avoid non-consistent environmental conditions inside the climatic chamber.

Observe the bees after 30 minutes and replace moribund individuals with healthy ones.

Record mortality and assess sub-lethal effects after 4, 8, 16 and 24 h since the exposure, and then daily every 24 h; use three categories to evaluate the bee conditions: alive – normally active and responsive, knocked down/moribund – inactive but still displaying response to a mechanical stimulus (touch or blowing) or dead. Reduced coordination or hyperactivity should be recorded to allow evaluation of sublethal effects.

Follow the survival until the control mortality reach 20% (or at least for 7 days). Control the food availability daily and supply the sucrose solution when needed – ensure that all bees are fed *ad libitum*.

5.5 Validity of the test

Mortality in control treatments should not exceed 20%.

5.6 Reporting

Results should be reported in an Excel spreadsheet as follows:

- Spreadsheet 1 – ‘Information sheet’: should include a text box with all crucial information about the test, such as a brief description of the test, origin/source of the bees, actual conditions of the test (temperature, humidity, light conditions, etc.), pesticide(s) used (active ingredient(s), formulation(s), producer, source), units used, etc., information on statistical method used to estimate LC50 and LT50 values.
- Spreadsheet 2 – ‘Raw data’: table containing the following variables (columns) (1) unique identifier (experimental box/bee number), (2) pesticide name/symbol, (3) concentration of the pesticide, (4) body mass of the bee, (5) date of starting the exposure, (6) date of death, (7) date of knocked down, (8) any additional information (e.g., sublethal effects, abnormalities, or other important information)

- Spreadsheet 2 – ‘results’: (1) LC50 values calculated for different exposure times (e.g., 24 h, 48 h, etc.) by fitting a dose-response probit or logit model; (2) LT50 value estimated from survival curves for each treatment.

* Range-finder experiment

If the range of concentrations to be tested in a dose-response experiment is unknown, determine first the tolerance limits of *O. bicornis* females to a pesticide in question. In a range-finder experiment follow the procedure described above using a broad geometric series of concentrations relative to recommended application concentrations for field conditions (RAC): 100×RAC, 10×RAC, 1×RAC and 0.1×RAC plus control. All solutions should be prepared in 0.1% Triton; for control treatment use 0.1% Triton solution.

Use 10 females per treatment for the range-finder, either kept individually or in group housing.

The lowest concentration causing ca. 90-100% mortality after 7 days of exposure should be selected as the highest one in the main experiment in which 50 females should be tested per concentration (n=50).

6 Red mason bee (*Osmia bicornis*) – determining the susceptibility to pesticides: continuous exposure of adults via food (group housing)

SOP reference number: UJ-2 (*Osmia* adult food exposure; continuous exposure, group housing)

6.1 Objective

Determination of the effects of a single pesticide on orally exposed adult females of *Osmia bicornis* – group exposure

6.2 Materials

6.2.1 Test substrate and food

- Sucrose solution (33% by weight)

6.2.2 Test animals

- Species: *Osmia bicornis* females obtained from a controlled culture initiated from commercially available cocoons of *O. bicornis*. Upon arrival from the commercial supplier, the cocoons are stored in a fridge at 4°C until spring.
- Life stage: newly emerged females, i.e., those individuals which survived at least 96 h after emerging from the cocoon.

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6.2.3 Test chemicals/stressors

- Pesticide of interest – a formulation or an active ingredient, depending on the goal of the test

6.2.4 Climatic conditions

(P = Photoperiod: Light/Dark (h); T = Temperature (°C); RH = Relative Humidity (%)) L = Light intensity (lux)

- Summer conditions: P: 16 L/8 D; T: 20°C; RH: 50%; L: ca. 10000-20000 lux

6.2.5 Parameters measured

- Mortality

6.2.6 Other necessary materials/equipment

- Climatic chambers
- Standard laboratory equipment
- Paper boxes with holes for cocoons

- Transparent plastic boxes with perforated lids (or covered with a mesh) – bigger (e.g., 46x30x17 cm - length/width/height) for bees culturing after their emergence from cocoons, smaller (e.g., 18.5x13.5x6.0 cm – length/width/height) for group housing in test
- Eppendorf tubes closed with cotton plugs and disposable plastic syringes (for sucrose solution to feed the bees)

6.3 Experimental setup

Exposure to a pesticide through food (sucrose solution): at least four pesticide concentrations (treatment solutions prepared in 33% sucrose solution) and a control (uncontaminated food, 33% sucrose solution), each in 5 replicates (10 bees per replicate). The concentrations for tested pesticide, if not known, should be selected based on the range-finder study (*see below a short description for the range-finding experiment**).

6.4 Procedures

6.4.1 Prepare food for bees

Prepare 33% sucrose solution (33 g sucrose in 100 g distilled water).

Prepare at least 4 pesticide concentrations in 33% sucrose solution and wrap the bottles with solutions with aluminum foil to avoid photodegradation. Store the solutions in a fridge (4°C) if not prepared on a day of the exposure. Store samples of all pesticide at -20°C for chemical analysis.

6.4.2 Emergence of *O. bicornis*

Transfer small paper boxes (e.g., 10x10x5 cm) containing cocoons from 4°C to summer conditions. Select larger cocoons to be emerged (ca. 100 cocoons per box of abovementioned size) to increase the fraction of females needed for the test (female cocoons are larger than male cocoons).

Place the boxes with cocoons in bigger transparent plastic box (46x30x17 cm length/width/height) with perforated lids to allow air exchange. The bees emerging in carton boxes will move into light where they can be collected.

Control the box for emerged bees at least twice a day and immediately remove males if noticed (males usually emerge earlier than females). Transfer the newly emerged females every day to a new breeding box - place the newly emerged, meconium-free female bees in a new box of the same kind as the emergence boxes but with a shelter for the bees (e.g., cardboard compartments from test-tube boxes) and a few Eppendorf tubes with sucrose solution (33%) closed with a cotton plug as a food source; attach an artificial “flower” made of sponge to the Eppendorf. Optionally provide

sucrose solution via disposable plastic syringes (e.g., 2 ml) with straight cropped tips and a yellow tape or sponge attached to its end simulating a flower.

Breed the bees *ad libitum*. for 72 hours adding food when needed.

After 3 days of feeding and 24 h before starting the experiment, remove the food (Eppendorf tubes or syringes with sucrose solution) from the breeding boxes.

Use only healthy bees for the test.

6.4.3 Running the experiment

Prepare plastic boxes (ca. 18x12x8 cm - length/width/height) with perforated lids (or covered with mesh) and two holes drilled in the wall of the box needed for inserting plastic syringes with food.

Label each box with a proper number and treatment ID (pesticide name, pesticide concentration in food, replicate) using a permanent marker.

Insert 2 ml plastic syringes with sucrose solution (contaminated or control) into the holes drilled in the wall of the box; to allow better access to the solution, crop the syringe tip and attach a piece of yellow “flower” around the cropped tip to increase visual attractiveness to bees and to allow easier access to food (landing place). Place a tissue paper covering the cage bottom.

Inactivate females by keeping them no longer than for 30 minutes at 4°C. Place 10 bees per replicate in one Petri dish and weigh them as a group to calculate average body mass.

Transfer 10 previously inactivated bees into test boxes (10 females per box, n=5) and place the boxes in the climatic chamber at summer conditions. Place boxes with treated and control bees at random to avoid non-consistent environmental conditions inside the climate chamber.

Observe the bees for 30 minutes and replace moribund individuals with healthy ones.

Store the bottles with food (both contaminated and uncontaminated sucrose solution) at the same conditions (i.e., in the same climatic chamber) as tested bees to have similar degradation of pesticide in both food provided in the syringes at the beginning of exposure and food stored for replenishment during the test.

Record mortality and assess sub-lethal effects after 4, 8, 16 and 24 h since the exposure, and then daily (every 24 h); use three categories to evaluate the bee conditions: alive – normally active and responsive, knocked down/moribund - inactive but still displaying response to a mechanical stimulus (touch or blowing) or dead. Reduced coordination or hyperactivity should be recorded to allow evaluation of sublethal effects.

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Follow the survival until the control mortality reach 20% (or at least for 7 days). Control the food availability daily and supply the sucrose solution when needed – ensure that all bees are fed *ad libitum*. If needed, replace a tissue paper covering the cage bottom.

6.5 Validity of the test

Mortality in control treatments should not exceed 20%.

6.6 Reporting

Results should be reported in an Excel spreadsheet as follows:

- Spreadsheet 1 – ‘Information sheet’: should include a text box with all crucial information about the test, such as a brief description of the test, origin/source of the bees, actual conditions of the test (temperature, humidity, light conditions, etc.), pesticide(s) used (active ingredient(s), formulation(s), producer, source), units used, etc., information on statistical method used to estimate LC₅₀ and LT₅₀ values.
- Spreadsheet 2 – ‘Raw data’: table containing the following variables (columns) (1) unique identifier (experimental box number), (2) pesticide name/symbol, (3) concentration of the pesticide, (4) average body mass of bees, (5) date of starting the exposure, (6) date of death, (7) date of knocked down, (8) any additional information (e.g., sublethal effects, abnormalities or other important information)
- Spreadsheet 2 – ‘results’: (1) LC₅₀ values calculated for different exposure times (e.g., 24 h, 48 h, etc.) by fitting a dose-response probit or logit model; (2) LT₅₀ value estimated from survival curves for each treatment.

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* Range-finder experiment

If the range of concentrations to be tested in a dose-response experiment is unknown, determine first the tolerance limits of *O. bicornis* females to a pesticide in question. In a range-finder experiment follow the procedure described above using a broad geometric series of concentrations relative to recommended application concentrations for field condition (RAC): 100×RAC, 10×RAC, 1×RAC and 0.1×RAC plus control. All solutions should be prepared in 33% sucrose solution; for control treatment use 33% sucrose solution.

Use 10 females per treatment for a range-finder.

The lowest concentration causing 90-100% mortality after 7 days of exposure should be selected as the highest one in the main experiment in which 50 females should be tested per concentration, 10 in each replicate (n=5).

7 Red mason bee (*Osmia bicornis*) – determining the susceptibility to pesticides: continuous exposure of adults via food (individual housing)

SOP reference number: UJ-3 (*Osmia* adult food exposure; continuous exposure, individual housing)

7.1 Objective

Determination of the effects of a single pesticide on orally exposed adult females of *Osmia bicornis* – individual exposure

7.2 Materials

7.2.1 Test substrate and food

- Sucrose solution (33% by weight)

7.2.2 Test animals

- Species: *Osmia bicornis* females obtained from a controlled culture initiated from commercially available cocoons of *O. bicornis*. Upon arrival from the commercial supplier, the cocoons are stored in a fridge at 4°C until spring.
- Life stage: newly emerged females, i.e., those individuals which survived at least 96 h after emerging from the cocoon.

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7.2.3 Test chemicals/stressors

- Pesticide of interest – a formulation or an active ingredient, depending on the goal of the test.

7.2.4 Climatic conditions

(P = Photoperiod: Light/Dark (h); T = Temperature (°C); RH = Relative Humidity (%) L = Light intensity (lux)

- Summer conditions: P: 16 L/8 D; T: 20°C; RH: 50%; L: 10000 – 20000 lux

7.2.5 Parameters measured

- Mortality
- Other necessary materials/equipment:
- Climatic chambers
- Standard laboratory equipment
- Paper boxes with holes for cocoons

- Transparent plastic boxes (e.g., 46x30x17 cm - length/width/height) with perforated lids (or covered with a mesh) for bees culturing after their emergence from cocoons
- Small plastic cups (ca. 500 ml) with perforated lids for individual housing
- Eppendorf tubes closed with a cotton plugs (for sucrose solution to feed the bee)

7.3 Experimental setup

Exposure to a pesticide through food (33% sucrose solution): at least four pesticide concentrations and control (uncontaminated food), each in 50 replicates (50 bees). The concentrations for tested pesticide, if not known, should be selected based on a range-finder study (*see below a short description for the range-finding experiment**).

7.4 Procedures

7.4.1 Prepare food for bees

Prepare 33% sucrose solution (33 g sucrose in 100 g distilled water).

Prepare at least 4 pesticide solutions (at least 4 pesticide treatments) in 33% sucrose solution and wrap the bottles with solutions with aluminum foil to avoid photodegradation. Store the solutions in a fridge (4°C) if not prepared on a day of exposure. Store samples of all pesticide solutions at -20°C for chemical analysis.

7.4.2 Emergence of *O. bicornis*

Transfer cocoons from 4°C to summer conditions. Select larger cocoons to be emerged to increase the fraction of females needed for the test (female cocoons are larger). Place ca. 100 cocoons per one cartoon box (ca. 10x10x5 cm).

Place the boxes with cocoons in bigger transparent plastic boxes (ca. 46x30x17 cm length/width/height) with perforated lids to allow air circulation. The bees emerging in cartoon boxes will move into light where they can be collected.

Control the box for emerged bees twice a day and immediately remove males if noticed (males usually emerge before females). Transfer the newly emerged females every day to a new breeding box - place the newly emerged, meconium-free female bees in a new box of the same kind as the plastic emergence boxes but with a shelter for the bees (e.g., cardboard compartments from test-tube boxes) and a few Eppendorf tubes with sucrose solution (33%) closed with a cotton plug as a food source; attach an artificial yellow “flower” made of sponge to the Eppendorf. Optionally provide sucrose solution via disposable plastic syringes (e.g., 2 ml) with straight cropped tips and yellow tape or sponge attached to its end simulating a flower.

Breed the bees *ad libitum* for 72 hours adding food when needed.

After 3 days of feeding and 24 h before starting the experiment., remove the food (Eppendorf tubes or syringes with sucrose solution) from the breeding boxes.

Use only healthy bees for the test.

7.4.3 Running the experiment

Prepare plastic test boxes (e.g., 500 ml cups) with perforated lids (or covered with mesh) and Eppendorf type 2 ml tube attached with a glue to the bottom of the cup. Prepare 250 boxes (4 pesticide treatments plus control), each in 50 replicates (n=50 bees per treatment).

Label each box with a proper number and treatment ID (pesticide name, pesticide concentration in food, replicate) using a permanent marker.

Put sucrose solution into each Eppendorf tube and close the tubes with cotton plugs; to allow better access to the solution attach a piece of yellow “flower” around the Eppendorf tube border.

Inactivate females by keeping them no longer than for 30 minutes at 4°C, weigh them and transfer to the boxes (50 females per treatment, n=50). Place the boxes with treated and control bees at random to avoid non-consistent environmental conditions inside the climate chamber.

Observe the bees for 30 minutes and replace moribund individuals with healthy ones.

Store the bottles with food (both contaminated and uncontaminated sucrose solution) at the same conditions (i.e., in the same climatic chamber) as tested bees to have similar degradation of pesticide in both food provided in the Eppendorf tubes and food stored as a food stored for replenishment during the test.

Record mortality and assess sub-lethal effects after 4, 8, 16 and 24 h since the exposure, and then daily (every 24 h); use the three categories to evaluate the bee conditions: alive – normally active and responsive, knocked down/moribund - inactive but still displaying response to a mechanical stimulus (touch or blowing) or dead. Reduced coordination or hyperactivity should be recorded to allow evaluation of sublethal effects.

Follow the survival until the control mortality reach 20% (or at least for 7 days). Control the food availability daily and supply the sucrose solution when needed – ensure that all bees are fed *ad libitum*.

7.5 Validity of the test

Mortality in control treatments should not exceed 20%.

7.6 Reporting

Results should be reported in an Excel spreadsheet as follows:

- Spreadsheet 1 – ‘Information sheet’: should include a text box with all crucial information about the test, such as a brief description of the test, origin/source of the bees, actual conditions of the test (temperature, humidity, light conditions, etc.), pesticide(s) used (active ingredient(s), formulation(s), producer, source), units used, etc., information on statistical method used to estimate LC50 and LT50 values.
- Spreadsheet 2 – ‘Raw data’: table containing the following variables (columns) (1) unique identifier (experimental box/bee number), (2) pesticide name/symbol, (3) concentration of the pesticide, (4) body mass of the bee, (5) date of starting the exposure, (6) date of death , (7) date of knocked down, (8) any additional information (e.g., sublethal effects, abnormalities or other important information).
- Spreadsheet 2 – ‘results’: (1) LC50 values calculated for different exposure times (e.g., 24 h, 48 h, etc.) by fitting a dose-response probit or logit model; (2) LT50 value estimated from survival curves for each treatment.

* Range-finder experiment

If the range of concentrations to be tested in a dose-response experiment is unknown, determine first the tolerance limits of *O. bicornis* females to a pesticide in question. In a range-finder experiment follow the procedure described above using a broad geometric series of concentrations relative to recommended application concentrations for field conditions (RAC): 100×RAC, 10×RAC, 1×RAC and 0.1×RAC plus control. All solutions should be prepared in 33% sucrose solution; for control treatment use 33% sucrose solution.

Use 10 females per treatment for the range-finder.

The lowest concentration causing ca. 90-100% mortality after 7 days of exposure should be selected as the highest one in the main experiment in which 50 females should be tested per concentration (n=50).

8 Red mason bee (*Osmia bicornis*) – determining the susceptibility to pesticides: test on adults exposed via food (individual exposure to exact pesticide dose)

SOP reference number: UJ-4 (*Osmia* adult food exposure; individual exposure to exact dose)

8.1 Objective

Determination of the effects of a single pesticide on orally exposed adult females of *Osmia bicornis* – individual exposure via food to the exact dose

8.2 Materials

8.2.1 Test substrate and food

- Sucrose solution (33% by weight)

8.2.2 Test animals

- Species: *Osmia bicornis* females obtained from a controlled culture initiated from commercially available cocoons of *O. bicornis*. Upon arrival from the commercial supplier, the cocoons are stored in a fridge at 4°C until spring.
- Life stage: newly emerged females, i.e., those individuals which survived at least 96 h after emerging from cocoons.

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8.2.3 Test chemicals/stressors

- Pesticide of interest – a formulation or an active ingredient, depending on the goal of the test.

8.2.4 Climatic conditions

(P = Photoperiod: Light/Dark (h); T = Temperature (°C); RH = Relative Humidity (%) L = Light intensity (lux)

- Summer conditions: P: 16 L/8 D; T: 20°C; RH: 50%; L: 10000 – 20000 lux

8.2.5 Parameters measured

- Mortality

8.2.6 Other necessary materials/equipment

- Climatic chambers
- Standard laboratory equipment
- Paper boxes with holes for cocoons

- Transparent plastic boxes (e.g., 46x30x17 cm - length/width/height) with perforated lids (or covered with a mesh) for bees culturing after their emergence from cocoons
- Small plastic cups (ca. 500 ml) with perforated lids for individual housing
- Small tubes/vials for offering bees the exact amount of sucrose solution

8.3 Experimental setup

Exposure to a pesticide through food (sucrose solution): at least four pesticide doses (treatment solutions prepared by diluting the test item with 33% sucrose solution) and control (uncontaminated food), each in 50 replicates (50 bees). The concentrations for tested pesticide, if not known, should be selected based on a range-finder study (*see below short description for the range-finding experiment**).

8.4 Procedures

8.4.1 Prepare food for bees

Prepare 33% sucrose solution (33 g sucrose in 100 g distilled water).

Prepare at least 4 pesticide concentrations in 33% sucrose solution and wrap the bottles with solutions with aluminum foil to avoid photodegradation. Store the solutions in a fridge (4°C) if not prepared on a day of the exposure. Store samples of all pesticide solutions at -20°C for chemical analysis.

8.4.2 Emergence of *O. bicornis*

Transfer cocoons from 4°C to summer conditions. Select larger cocoons to be emerged to increase the fraction of females needed for the test (female cocoons are larger). Place ca. 100 cocoons per one carton box (ca. 10x10x5 cm).

Place the boxes with cocoons in bigger transparent plastic boxes (ca. 46x30x17 cm length/width/height) with perforated lids to allow air circulation. The bees emerging in carton boxes will move into light where they can be collected.

Control the boxes for emerged bees twice a day and immediately remove males if noticed (males usually emerge before females). Transfer the newly emerged females every day to a new breeding box - place the newly emerged, meconium-free female bees in a new box of the same kind as the plastic emergence boxes but with a shelter for the bees (e.g., cardboard compartments from test-tube boxes) and a few Eppendorf tubes with sucrose solution (33%) closed with a cotton plug as a food source; attach an artificial yellow “flower” made of sponge to the Eppendorf. Optionally

provide sucrose solution via disposable plastic syringes (e.g., 2 ml) with straight cropped tips and a yellow tape or sponge attached to its end simulating a flower.

Breed the bees *ad libitum* for 72 hours adding food when needed.

After 3 days of feeding and 24 h before starting the exposure, remove the food (Eppendorf tubes or syringes with sucrose solution) from the breeding boxes.

Use only healthy bees for the test.

8.4.3 Running the experiment

Prepare plastic test boxes (e.g., 500 ml cups) with perforated lids or covered with mesh and small tube/vial attached with a glue to the bottom of the cup**. Prepare 250 boxes (4 treatments plus control), each in 50 replicates (n=50 bees per treatment).

Label each box with a proper number and treatment ID (pesticide name, pesticide concentration, replicate) using a permanent marker.

Put 10 µl of sucrose solution (contaminated or control) into each tube/vial attached to the box; to allow better access to the solution attach an artificial yellow “flower” around the tube/vial border to increase visual attractiveness to bees and allow easier access to food (landing place).

Inactivate females by keeping them no longer than for 30 minutes at 4°C, weigh them and transfer to the box.

Observe the bees up to 2 hours if consumed all amount of solution. Use only those bees which consumed the whole food in the experiment.

Afterwards, replace the tubes/vials with uncontaminated sucrose solution and place the boxes in the climatic chamber at summer conditions. Place the boxes with treated and control bees at random to avoid non-consistent environmental conditions inside the climate chamber.

Record mortality and assess sub-lethal effects after 4, 8, 16 and 24 h since the exposure, and then daily every 24 h; use three categories to evaluate the bee conditions: alive – normally active and responsive, knocked down/moribund - inactive but still displaying response to a mechanical stimulus (touch or blowing) or dead. Reduced coordination or hyperactivity should be recorded to allow evaluation of sublethal effects.

Follow the survival until the control mortality reach 20% (or at least for 7 days). Control the food availability twice a day and supply the sucrose solution when needed (preferably twice a day) – ensure that all bees are fed *ad libitum*.

8.5 Validity of the test

Mortality in control treatments should not exceed 20%.

8.6 Reporting

Results should be reported in an Excel spreadsheet as follows:

- Spreadsheet 1 – ‘Information sheet’: should include a text box with all crucial information about the test, such as a brief description of the test, origin/source of the bees, actual conditions of the test (temperature, humidity, light conditions, etc.), pesticide(s) used (active ingredient(s), formulation(s), producer, source), units used, etc., information on statistical method used to estimate LC50 and LT50 values.
- Spreadsheet 2 – ‘Raw data’: table containing the following variables (columns) (1) unique identifier (experimental box/bee number), (2) pesticide name/symbol, (3) concentration of the pesticide, (4) body mass of the bee, (5) date of starting the exposure, (6) date of death, (7) date of knocked down, (8) any additional information (e.g., sublethal effects, abnormalities or other important information)
- Spreadsheet 2 – ‘results’: (1) LC50 values calculated for different exposure times (e.g., 24 h, 48 h, etc.) by fitting a dose-response probit or logit model; (2) LT50 value estimated from survival curves for each treatment.

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* Range-finder experiment

If the range of concentrations to be tested in a dose-response experiment is unknown, determine the tolerance limits of *O. bicornis* females to a pesticide in question. In a range-finder experiment follow the procedure described using a broad geometric series of concentrations relative to recommended application concentrations for field conditions (RAC): 100×RAC, 10×RAC, 1×RAC and 0.1×RAC plus control. All solutions should be prepared in 33% sucrose solution; for control treatment use 33% sucrose solution.

Use 10 females per treatment for the rangefinder.

The lowest concentration causing ca. 90-100% mortality after 7 days of exposure should be selected as the highest one in the main experiment in which 50 females should be tested per concentration (n=50).

** Alternatively, Nicot cages with attached small plastic syringes (1 mL) can be used for individual exposure and housing. If exposure via syringes is used, then syringes have to be weighted before

and after the 2 h exposure to determine the amount of test solution consumed. Afterwards, syringes should be replaced with the ones with sucrose solution.

9 Red mason bee (*Osmia bicornis*) – determining the susceptibility to pesticides: test on different developmental stages

SOP reference number: UJ-5 (*Osmia* larvae food exposure, individual housing)

9.1 Objective

Determination of the effects of a single pesticide on developmental stages of *Osmia bicornis* (from larvae to adult).

9.2 Materials

9.2.1 Test substrate and food

- Standard multifloral pollen (moisture of ca. 10%)
- Test animals:
- Species: *Osmia bicornis* larvae obtained from a controlled culture initiated from commercially available cocoons of *O. bicornis*. Upon arrival from the commercial supplier, the cocoons are stored at 4°C until spring.
- Life stage: 3-day old larvae

9.2.2 Test chemicals/stressors

- Pesticide of interest – a formulation or an active ingredient, depending on the goal of the test.

9.2.3 Climatic conditions

(P = Photoperiod: Light/Dark (h); T = Temperature (°C); RH = Relative Humidity (%); L = Light intensity (lux))

- Summer conditions: P: 16 L/8 D; T: 20°C; RH: 50%; L: 10000-20000 lux
- Autumn conditions: P: 12 L/12 D; T: 15°C; RH: 40%; L: ca. 8000 lux
- Winter conditions: T: 8°C; RH: 30% (reduced humidity to avoid fungal growth on the formed cocoons); L: darkness

9.2.4 Parameters measured

- Mortality, body mass of 21-day old larvae, time required to start cocoon formation, cocoon mass before and after overwintering, rate of emergence from cocoon (to be recorded in the spring next year).

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9.2.5 Other necessary materials/equipment

- Climatic chambers
- Standard laboratory equipment
- Transparent Eppendorf tubes of 2 ml capacity with a hole in the lid
- Transparent plastic boxes (e.g., 46x30x17 cm - length/width/height) with perforated lids (or covered with a mesh) for bees culturing after their emergence from cocoons
- Food mixer (blender)

9.3 Experimental setup

Exposure to a pesticide through food (pollen): at least four pesticide concentrations and control (uncontaminated pollen), each in 50 replicates (starting with 50 individuals of 3-day old larvae, one individual per Eppendorf tube). Test concentrations of the pesticide should be selected based on available data or on a range-finder study on larvae (*see below a short description of the range-finding experiment**).

9.4 Procedures

9.4.1 Prepare food for larvae

Grind the pollen using food mixer.

Check the dry mass of pollen (based on at least three samples).

Prepare all tested pesticide solutions (four pesticide treatments and distilled water as control) and wrap the bottles with solutions with aluminum foil to avoid photodegradation. Store the solutions in a fridge (4°C) if not prepared on a day of exposure. Store samples of all pesticide solutions at -20°C for chemical analysis.

Calculate required volumes of solutions to be added to obtain both the desired concentration of a pesticide in pollen (ng/g) and the required moisture of the contaminated pollen of ca. 20% (i.e., the moisture of pollen observed in the bee cells in the field).

Mix the given amount of pollen with the calculated volume of either pesticide solution or distilled water using food mixer. For those active ingredients (a.i.) which need to be dissolved in an organic solvent (acetone) prepare proper solutions, mix the pollen with the volume of the solution required to obtain desired concentration of a.i. in pollen, let the acetone to evaporate by leaving the contaminated pollen for 2 hours under the fume hood and add distilled water to obtain 20% moisture of pollen. Remember to include control for acetone as an additional treatment in the test. Store the samples of pollen (treated with a pesticide and control) at -20°C for chemical analysis.

Label each Eppendorf tube with a proper number and treatment ID using a permanent marker.

Make a hole in the lid.

Put 200 mg of pollen into each Eppendorf tube, close the tubes and store them at -20°C until needed.

9.4.2 Emergence of *O. bicornis*

Transfer cocoons from 4°C together with nest cages (wooden or plastic cage with wooden or plastic nesting channels; it is crucial that the channels are easy to inspect daily) to the field at a ratio of 200 cocoons per 100 nesting channels; place the nest facing south near good floral resources and make little opening in the cocoon box to allow the emerged bees to leave the box.

Label the nesting channels with numbers.

Allow the bees to hatch (two to three days for males and five to six days for females) and mate, collect pollen and lay eggs.

9.4.3 Running the experiment

Observe the status of the nest daily.

Starting a week after observing first emerged females inspect the nest in the lab daily; carefully open each layer of nesting channels and record the number of closed cells (cell with pollen and egg closed with a mud wall) and the age of larvae in days.

With utmost care, using a brush or a spatula, transfer each 3-day old larvae to the previously prepared Eppendorf tubes with pollen. Remember to unfreeze the tubes with pollen early enough to bring the pollen to room temperature before placing the larvae. Transfer the larvae to different treatments randomly, so that larvae from one nesting channel are assigned to different treatments. While assigning larvae to treatments try to keep similar sex ratio in different treatments by taking into account that female eggs are deposited first, i.e., in the deepest cells of the nesting channels.

Return the nest to its original place.

Continue steps 3.6 - 3.8 daily until the required number of larvae are collected and placed in experimental tubes.

Place the Eppendorf tubes with larvae at summer conditions (P: 16 L/8 D; T: 20°C; RH: 40%) in darkness and inspect the larvae daily; record the date of death and assess any sub-lethal effects and abnormalities till cocoon formation.

Weigh each larva at 18th day of the exposure (i.e., record body mass of 21-day old larvae).

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Continue checking survival of the larvae daily till cocoon formation. Record the date of cocoon formation.

Keep the Eppendorf tubes with cocoons at summer conditions for four weeks and then, after weighing, transfer them to autumn conditions for 4 weeks and to winter conditions for at least 14 weeks.

After overwintering, weigh the cocoons and transfer them to summer conditions to let the bees emerge.

Record the date of emerging of adults, their sex and body mass (for weighing inactivate the emerged bees by putting them for approximately 30 minutes into the fridge at 4°C).

Release the emerged bees or transfer them to plastic culturing boxes for group housing if needed for further studies (*see point 3.2. Emergence of O. bicornis in SOP number UJ-1*).

9.5 Validity of the test

Mortality at larval stage till cocoon formation in control treatments should not exceed 20%.

9.6 Reporting

Results should be reported in an Excel spreadsheet as follows:

- Spreadsheet 1 – ‘Information sheet’: should include a text box with all crucial information about the test, such as a brief description of the test, origin/source of the bees, actual conditions of the test (temperature, humidity, light conditions, etc.), pesticide(s) used (active ingredient(s), formulation(s), producer, source), units used, etc., information on statistical method used to estimate LC50 and LT50 values.
- Spreadsheet 2 – ‘Raw data’: table containing the following variables (columns) (1) unique identifier (experimental tube/larvae number), (2) pesticide name/symbol, (3) concentration of the pesticide, (4) date of starting the exposure of an individual larvae, (6) date of death, (7) body mass of 21-day old larvae, (8) date of cocoon formation, (9) cocoon mass before overwintering, (10) cocoon mass after overwintering, (11) date of cocoon transferring to summer conditions, (12) date of emergence from cocoon, (13) sex, (14) body mass of emerged adult, (15) any additional information (e.g., sublethal effects, abnormalities or other important information)
- Spreadsheet 2 – ‘results’: (1) LC50 values calculated for different exposure by fitting a dose-response probit or logit model; (2) LT50 value estimated from survival curves for each treatment.

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* Range-finder experiment

If the range of concentrations to be tested in a dose-response experiment is unknown, determine first the tolerance limits of *O. bicornis* larvae to a pesticide in question. In a range-finder experiment follow the procedure described above using a broad geometric series of concentrations relative to recommended application concentrations for field conditions (RAC): 100×RAC, 10×RAC, 1×RAC and 0.1×RAC plus control. All solutions should be prepared in distilled water (or acetone in case of using water-insoluble active ingredients) and added to the pollen at a volume to reach the final moisture of 20%. If acetone is used as a solvent, follow the procedure described for the main experiment to evaporate the acetone and reach the 20% moisture by adding distilled water.

Use 10 larvae per treatment for the rangefinder, kept individually in Eppendorf tubes with pollen.

The lowest concentration causing ca. 90-100% mortality after 21 days of larval exposure should be selected as the highest one in the main experiment in which 50 larvae should be tested per concentration.

10 Carabid beetles (Carabidae) and ladybirds (Coccinellidae) – acute toxicity test on adults: contact exposure using Potter Tower spray of Petri dishes

SOP reference number: UJ-6

10.1 Objective

Determination of the effects of a single pesticide spray on a selected beetle species on a Petri dish using Potter tower – imitation of field spraying of crops with pesticides

10.2 Materials

10.2.1 Test animals

- Species: Beetle species (Coleoptera) considered as Ecosystem Services Providers. Species of interest should be collected and kept in climatic chamber as described in: SOP UJ-8 for Carabidae species and UJ-9 for Coccinellidae species. Individuals should be moved to the climatic chamber (conditions below) at least 24 h before experiment. All ill-looking, slowly moving, discolored or defected specimens should be excluded from experiment. Exemplary species of interest:
- Carabid beetles (Carabidae; natural enemies of crop pests; e.g., *Amara ovata*, *Amara similata*, *Bembidion lampros*, *Calathus fuscipes*, *Harpalus rufipes*, *Harpalus signaticornis*, *Poecilus cupreus*, *Pterostichus melanarius*)
- Ladybirds (Coccinellidae; natural enemies of aphids and other crop pests; e.g. *Coccinella septempunctata*)
- Life stage: adults

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10.2.2 Climatic conditions:

(P = Photoperiod: Light/Dark (h); T = Temperature (°C); RH = Relative Humidity (%) L = Light intensity (lux)

- Summer conditions: P: 16 L/8 D; T: 20°C; RH: 70%; L: ca. 10000-20000 lux

10.2.3 Parameters measured

- individual's condition ('mobile' / 'affected' / 'knocked down' / 'dead'). Both 'knocked down' and 'dead' individuals are considered as 'ecologically dead' as under natural conditions they would not survive.

10.3 Other necessary materials/equipment

- Potter Tower

- Climatic chambers
- Standard laboratory equipment
- 15 Petri dishes of uniform diameter (e.g. 8 cm)

10.4 Experimental setup

Exposure to a pesticide via contact with sprayed surface (Potter Tower spray of water solution of pesticide): at least four pesticide doses (treatment solutions prepared by diluting the test item with deionized water) and one control (distilled water), each in 3 replicates. In each replicate (Petri dish) placing 5-10 individuals is recommended, depending on the species abundance and size.

10.5 Procedures

10.5.1 Calculations (with the examples*)

Obtain values of recommended volume of pesticide and solvent (water) per ha.

* For example: 0,15 l of 'Karate Zeon 050 CS' dissolved in 300 L of water is recommended per 1 ha.

Obtain the information about active ingredient amount in the pesticide.

* 1 L of 'Karate Zeon 050 CS' contains 50 g of active ingredient (lambda-cyhalothrin).

Calculate the amount of active ingredient per cm² and the volume of the solution to be present in cm².

* 300 L/ha = 3 µl/cm². For of 'Karate Zeon 050 CS' 3 µl of recommended pesticide solution contains 75 ng of active ingredient.

Calculate the amount of active ingredient and the volume of the solution to be present in a Petri dish for selected doses.

* For Petri dish of diameter = 8 cm, the area is $(4 \text{ cm})^2 \cdot 3.14 = 50.24 \text{ cm}^2$. If 3 µL of solution should be present in cm². Volume of the pesticide solution to be present in a Petri dish is: $3 \text{ µL/cm}^2 \cdot 50.24 \text{ cm}^2 = 150.72 \text{ µL}$.

10.5.2 Calibration of the Potter Tower

The Pressure in the Potter Tower should be set to 5 PSI. Pressure can fluctuate about 0.1 PSI

Spraying should be measured by timer and last for 10 seconds.

Make sure that the glass tube for pesticide spray is properly installed.

Add distilled water to the glass tube by pipette to the Potter Tower

* e.g. 3 mL

Gently wipe off water from the upper rim of Petri dish (surface not available for insects) and quickly weight Petri dish before the distilled water evaporates.

Compare the received weight to the calculated volume (1 μL of the solution is considered to weight 1 mg).

* e.g., expected weight of the solution is 150.72 mg.

Adjust the weight by adding water to the glass tube of the Potter tower.

If the obtained weight of the solution is similar to the expected one, make 10 repetitions of spraying to check the standard deviation of the amount sprayed. Calculate the mean and the standard deviation. The difference between expected weight and obtained mean shouldn't be higher/lower than 5% of the expected weight. Standard deviation shouldn't be higher than 10% of the mean. If the criteria are not met, find the cause, and calibrate Potter Tower again.

10.5.3 Preparation of the Potter Tower, solutions, and animals

Prepare at least 4 pesticide concentrations in distilled water and wrap the bottles with solutions with aluminum foil to avoid photodegradation. Store the solutions in a fridge (4°C) if not prepared on a day of exposure.

Individuals should be put in small empty plastic boxes on the day of the experiment for quicker placing them on Petri dishes. Number of the individuals should correspond to the number that will be placed on the Petri dish.

Prior to starting the experiment, make sure to clean the Potter tower and flush with 3 mL each of acetone (thrice), ethanol (thrice), distilled water (thrice) followed by the pesticide solution to be tested (once). Make sure that the glass tube for pesticide spray is properly installed.

Label each Petri dish and the lid

10.6 Running the experiment

Spray the control Petri dishes with distilled water first.

Spray pesticides solution, starting from the lowest concentration.

After spraying all Petri dishes with one concentration of the pesticide wash out the tower with the next (higher) concentration of the pesticide.

Continue the step 4.4.3 till all the Petri dishes are sprayed.

Clean the Potter tower and flush with 3 mL each of acetone (thrice), ethanol (thrice), distilled water (thrice).

After 30 minutes check if the water on Petri dishes has evaporated. If so, place animals on Petri dishes and put lids on them.

Arrange Petri dishes in the trays in the random way.

Transfer the trays to climatic chambers with standard conditions (climatic conditions given above (2.2)).

Evaluate the condition of each individual after 5, 24, 48 h since the exposure. Use four categories to evaluate the beetle condition:

- 'mobile' – normally active and responsive
- 'affected' – range of abnormal behaviour: from being able to cross at least 3 cm distance in a line to active but showing small signs of paralysis of legs
- 'knocked down' – not able to move but still responding to mechanical stimuli
- 'dead' – not responding to mechanical stimuli

10.7 Reporting

- Results should be reported in an Excel spreadsheet as follows:
- Spreadsheet 1 – 'Information sheet': should include all crucial information about the test, such as a brief description of test, collection sites, actual conditions of the test (temperature, humidity, light conditions, etc.), pesticide(s) used (active ingredient(s), formulation(s), producer, source), units used, etc., information on statistical method used to estimate LC₅₀ and LT₅₀ values.
- Spreadsheet 2 – 'Raw data': table containing the following variables (columns) (1) unique identifier (Petri dish label), (2) pesticide name/symbol, (3) concentration of the pesticide (4) date of starting the experiment, (5) date of death, (6) date of knocked down, (7) any additional information
- Spreadsheet 3 – 'Results': (1) LC₅₀ values calculated for different exposure times (e.g., 24 h, 48 h, etc.) by fitting a dose-response probit or logit model; (2) LT₅₀ value estimated from survival curves for each treatment.

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11 Beetles (Coleoptera) – acute toxicity test on adults: contact exposure using Potter Tower spray of soil

SOP reference number: UJ-7

11.1 Objective

Determination of the effects of a single pesticide spray on a selected beetle species on soil using Potter tower – imitation of field spraying of crops with pesticides.

11.2 Materials

11.2.1 Test animals:

- Species: Beetle species (Coleoptera) considered as Ecosystem Services Providers. Species of interest should be collected and kept in climatic chamber as described in: SOP UJ-8 for Carabidae species and UJ-9 for Coccinellidae species. Individuals should be moved to the climatic chamber (conditions below) at least 24h before experiment. All ill-looking, slowly moving, discolored or defected specimens should be excluded from experiment. Exemplary species of interest:
- Carabid beetles (Carabidae; natural enemies of crop pests; e.g. *Amara ovata*, *Amara similata*, *Bembidion lampros*, *Calathus fuscipes*, *Harpalus rufipes*, *Harpalus signaticornis*, *Poecilus cupreus*, *Pterostichus melanarius*)
- Ladybirds (Coccinellidae; natural enemies of aphids and other crop pests; e.g. *Coccinella septempunctata*)
- Life stage: adults

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11.2.2 Climatic conditions:

(P = Photoperiod: Light/Dark (h); T = Temperature (°C); RH = Relative Humidity (%) L = Light intensity (lux)

- Summer conditions: P: 16 L/8 D; T: 20°C; RH: 70%; L: ca. 10000-20000 lux

11.2.3 Parameters measured:

- Individual's condition ('mobile' / 'affected' / 'knocked down' / 'dead'). Both 'knocked down' and 'dead' individuals are considered as "ecologically dead" as in the natural environment they would not survive.

11.3 Other necessary materials/equipment:

- Potter Tower

- Climatic chambers
- Standard laboratory equipment
- 15 plastic boxes with lids (e.g., diameter 5.9 cm)
- LUFA 2.2 soil

11.4 Experimental setup

Exposure to a pesticide via contact with sprayed surface (Potter Towers spray of water solution of pesticide) at least four pesticide doses (treatment solutions prepared by diluting the test item with deionized water) and one control (distilled water), each in 3 replicates. In each replicate (box with soil) placing 5-10 individuals is recommended, depending on the species abundance and size.

11.5 Procedures

11.5.1 Calculations (with the examples*)

Obtain values of recommended volume of pesticide and solvent (water) per ha.

* For example: 0.15 L of 'Karate Zeon 050 CS' dissolved in 300 L of water is recommended per 1 ha.

Obtain the information about active ingredient amount in the pesticide.

* 1 L of 'Karate Zeon 050 CS' contains 50 g of active ingredient (lambda-cyhalothrin).

Calculate the amount of active ingredient per cm^2 and the volume of the solution to be present in cm^2 .

* $300 \text{ L/ha} = 3 \mu\text{L/cm}^2$. For of 'Karate Zeon 050 CS' $3 \mu\text{L}$ of recommended pesticide solution contains 75 ng of active ingredient.

Calculate the amount of active ingredient and the volume of the solution to be present in a Petri dish for selected doses.

* For box of diameter = 5.9 cm, area is $(2.95 \text{ cm})^2 * 3,14 = 27.33 \text{ cm}^2$. If $3 \mu\text{L}$ of solution should be present in cm^2 . Volume of the pesticide solution to be present in a Petri dish is: $3 \mu\text{L/cm} * 27.33 \text{ cm}^2 = 81.98 \mu\text{L}$.

11.5.2 Prepare the soil

Dry LUFA 2.2 soil in an oven at 105°C for 24 hours

After drying, let the LUFA 2.2 soil cool down to room temperature.

Prepare 1 kg of dried LUFA 2.2 soil to 50% of its water holding capacity (WHC) and then let the soil absorb water for one day (maximum WHC of LUFA 2.2 is 45.8 g of H_2O per 100 g of soil).

Prepare test boxes with 70 g of wet soil per cup (to form a 2 cm soil layer).

11.5.3 Calibration of the Potter Tower

The Pressure in the Potter Tower should be set to 5 PSI. Pressure can fluctuate about 0.1 PSI

Spraying should be measured by timer and last for 10 seconds.

Make sure that the glass tube for pesticide spray is properly installed.

Add distilled water to the glass tube by pipette to the Potter Tower

* e.g., 3 mL

Gently wipe off water from the upper rim of plastic box (surface not available for insects) and quickly weight plastic box before the distilled water evaporates.

Compare the received weight to the calculated volume (*1 μl of the solution is considered to weight 1 mg).

* e.g., expected weight of the solution is 81.98 mg.

Adjust the weight by adding water to the glass tube of the Potter tower.

If the obtained weight of the solution is similar to the expected one, make 10 repetitions of spraying to check the standard deviation of the amount sprayed. Calculate the mean and the standard deviation. The difference between expected weight and obtained mean shouldn't be higher/lower than 5% of the expected weight. Standard deviation shouldn't be higher than 10% of the mean. If the criteria are not met, find the cause, and calibrate Potter Tower again.

11.5.4 Prepare the Potter Tower, solutions and animals

Prepare at least 4 pesticide concentrations in distilled water and wrap the bottles with solutions with aluminum foil to avoid photodegradation. Store the solutions in a fridge (4°C) if not prepared on a day of exposure.

Individuals should be put in small empty plastic boxes on the day of the experiment for quicker placing them in the test boxes. Number of the individuals should correspond to the number that will be placed in the box with soil.

Prior to starting the experiment, make sure to clean the Potter tower and flush with 3 mL each of acetone (thrice), ethanol (thrice), distilled water (thrice) followed by the pesticide solution to be tested (once). Make sure that the glass tube for pesticide spray is properly installed.

Label each box and the lid. Make small holes in the plastic lid

11.6 Running the experiment

Spray the control boxes with distilled water first.

Spray pesticides solution, starting from the lowest concentration.

After spraying all boxes with one concentration of the pesticide wash out the tower with the next (higher) concentration of the pesticide.

After 30 minutes, place animals into boxes and put lids on them.

Arrange boxes in the trays in the random way.

Transfer the trays to climatic chambers with standard conditions (climatic conditions given above (2.2)).

Evaluate the condition of each individual after 5, 24, 48 h since the exposure. Use four categories to evaluate the beetle condition:

- ‘mobile’ – normally active and responsive
- ‘affected’ – range of abnormal behaviour: from being able to cross at least 3 cm distance in a line to active but showing small signs of paralysis of legs
- ‘knocked down’ – not able to move but still responding to mechanical stimuli
- ‘dead’ – not responding to mechanical stimuli

11.7 Reporting

Results should be reported in an Excel spreadsheet as follows:

- Spreadsheet 1 – ‘Information sheet’: should include all crucial information about the test, such as a brief description of test, collection sites, actual conditions of the test (temperature, humidity, light conditions, etc.), pesticide(s) used (active ingredient(s), formulation(s), producer, source), units used, etc., information on statistical method used to estimate LC50 and LT50 values.
- Spreadsheet 2 – ‘Raw data’: table containing the following variables (columns) (1) unique identifier, (2) pesticide name/symbol, (3) concentration of the pesticide (4) date of starting the experiment, (5) date of death, (6) date of knocked down, (7) any additional information
- Spreadsheet 3 – ‘Results’: (1) LC50 values calculated for different exposure times (e.g., 24 h, 48 h, etc.) by fitting a dose-response probit or logit model; (2) LT50 value estimated from survival curves for each treatment.

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12 Carabid beetles (Carabidae) – collecting using pitfall traps and maintaining the culture

SOP reference number: UJ-8

12.1 Objective

Obtaining carabid beetles (Carabidae) individuals for ecotoxicological tests.

12.2 Materials

12.2.1 Food:

- Food: Mix of mealworms (*Tenebrio molitor* larvae) and apple (proportion 8 parts mealworms : 1 part apple)

12.2.2 Animals:

- Species: Carabidae beetles species considered as Ecosystem Services Providers being natural enemies of many crop pests: *Amara ovata*, *Amara simillata*, *Bembidion lampros*, *Calathus fuscipes*, *Harpalus rufipes*, *Harpalus signaticornis*, *Poecilus cupreus*, *Pterostichus melanarius*
- Life stage: adults

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12.2.3 Climatic conditions

(P = Photoperiod: Light/Dark (h); T = Temperature (°C); RH = Relative Humidity (%) L = Light intensity (lux))

- Summer conditions: P: 16 L/8 D; T: 20°C; RH: 50%; L: 10000 – 20000 lux

12.2.4 Sampling season:

- depending on the crop type. Sampling should be performed after crop germination and before harvest.

12.2.5 Other necessary materials/equipment:

- Climatic chambers
- Pitfall traps (50 traps per one transect)
- Transparent plastic boxes (e.g., 30x30x15 cm - length/width/height) with perforated lids (or covered with a mesh) for beetles culturing. Density of beetles kept in a box should not exceed: 1 beetle/25 cm² – large species (e.g., *Pterostichus melanarius*), 1 beetles/12.5 cm² – smaller species (e.g., *Amara ovata*).

- * Carabidae beetles can attack each other when the density is too high.
- Frozen mealworms
- Apple baby food (e.g., Gerber®)
- Blender
- Plastic lab tubes for the frozen food
- Uncontaminated soil
- Pieces of broken ceramic pots (allow beetles to hide)
- Sprinkler with tap water

12.3 Procedures

12.3.1 Prepare food for beetles

Defreeze mealworms.

Blend mealworms together with apple baby food in the proportion: 8 parts mealworms and 1 part apple (e.g., 800 mL of mealworms: 100 mL of apple).

Prepared food can be stored frozen, e.g., in the plastic lab tubes.

12.3.2 Collect beetles

Select sampling fields. Fields should not be smaller than 1 ha. Sampling is recommended from oil-seed rape and winter wheat crops.

Place pitfall traps along the transect. Transect should be set alongside field margin. Recommended distance between pitfall traps is 1 m, therefore the total length of the transect should be c.a. 50 m.

After 2 days empty the pitfall traps. If the weather conditions are severe (e.g., heavy rain, heat waves) empty the pitfall traps more often.

Sort collected individuals by morphospecies and place them inside the boxes with perforated lids.

The boxes should be filled with thin layer of soil (1-2 cm) and pieces of broken ceramic pots.

Label each box with the date of collection, species name and number of individuals.

Transport boxes with individuals to climatic chamber (climatic conditions are given in 2.3).

12.3.3 Maintaining the culture

(should be repeated every second day)

Defreeze required amount of food.

Remove uneaten food, molded soil and dead individuals.

If substantial part of soil was removed add fresh soil.

If needed moisturize the soil using sprinkler with tap water.

Add food to each box (the amount of food depends on the number of individuals and their size; e.g. 1 ml of food per 20 *Pterostichus melanarius* individuals).

13 Ladybirds (Coccinellidae) – collecting and maintaining the culture

SOP reference number: UJ-9

13.1 Objective

Obtaining ladybird (Coccinellidae) individuals for ecotoxicological tests.

13.2 Materials

13.2.1 Food:

- Food: Alive aphids (Aphidae) collected from the uncontaminated environment.

13.2.2 Animals:

- Ladybirds (Coccinellidae; natural enemies of aphids and other crop pests; e.g. *Coccinella septempunctata*)
- Life stage: adults

13.2.3 Climatic conditions

(P = Photoperiod: Light/Dark (h); T = Temperature (°C); RH = Relative Humidity (%) L = Light intensity (lux))

- Summer conditions: P: 16 L/8 D; T: 20°C; RH: 50%; L: 10000 – 20000 lux

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13.2.4 Sampling season:

- Sampling should be performed after crop germination and before harvest.

13.2.5 Other necessary materials/equipment:

- Climatic chambers
- Transparent plastic boxes (e.g., 30x30x15 cm – length/width/height) with perforated lids (or covered with a mesh) for beetles culturing.
- Alive aphids

13.3 Procedures

13.3.1 Collect food for beetles

The aphids should be collected from uncontaminated places. Harvest parts of plants infected by aphids.

13.3.2 Collect Coccinellidae beetles

Select sampling fields. Fields should not be smaller than 1 ha. Sampling is recommended from oil-seed rape and winter wheat crops.

Coccinellidae should be hand-collected (safety gloves are recommended).

Sort collected individuals by morphospecies and place them inside the boxes with perforated lids.

The boxes should be filled with aphid-infected plants.

Label each box with the date of collection, species name and number of individuals.

Transport boxes with individuals to climatic chamber (climatic conditions are given in 2.3).

13.3.3 Maintaining the culture

(should be repeated every second day)

Remove molded plants and dead individuals.

If needed moisturize the plants using sprinkler with tap water.

Add aphid-infected plants to each box (the amount of food depends on the number of individuals).

14 Coated glass vials test – preparation of lambda-cyhalothrin coated vials

SOP reference number: UJ -10

14.1 Objective

Preparation of lambda-cyhalothrin coated glass vials for acute contact tests

14.2 Materials

14.2.1 Necessary materials/equipment

- Technical grade lambda-cyhalothrin (available from Sigma)
- Technical-grade acetone
- Glass vials which are 5 cm high x 2 cm in diameter (having an internal glass surface area of 34.56 cm², suggested supplier is S Murray and Co, Holborn House, High St, Old Woking, Woking, GU22 9LB, UK:)
- Roller
- Fridge (4°C)
- Standard laboratory equipment

14.3 Procedures

14.3.1 Prepare solutions

Procedure to prepare 10.2, 5.1, 1.02, 0.204, 0.041 ppm lambda-cyhalothrin solutions in acetone. These equate to 150, 75, 15, 3, 0.6 ng a.i./cm² (200%, 100%, 20%, 4%, 0.8% field rate respectively) when a volume of 500 µL is used per vial.

If needed prepare the stock solution. To obtain stock solution (1000 ppm) Add **10 mg** of technical lambda-cyhalothrin to the flask and dissolve it in **10 mL** of acetone. Vortex the solution. Stock solution can be stored in the dark at 4°C.

Prepare the range of concentrations.

Add **0.51 mL** of stock solution (1000 ppm) to volumetric flask (**50 cm³**) and fill it to volume with acetone to obtain 50 mL of 10.2 ppm solution. Vortex the solution.

Add **12.5 mL** of 10.2 ppm solution to volumetric flask (**25 cm³**) and fill it to volume with acetone to obtain 25 mL of 5.1 ppm solution. Vortex the solution.

Add **5 mL** of 5.1 ppm solution to volumetric flask (**25 cm³**) and fill it to volume with acetone to obtain 25 mL of 1.02 ppm solution. Vortex the solution.

Add **5 mL** of 1.02 ppm solution to volumetric flask (**25 cm³**) and fill it to volume with acetone to obtain 25 mL of 0.204 ppm solution. Vortex the solution.

Add **5 mL** of 0.204 ppm solution to volumetric flask (**25 cm³**) and fill it to volume with acetone to obtain 25 mL of 0.041 ppm solution. Vortex the solution.

Store the solutions in the dark at room temperature (if used the same day) or at 4°C (if used the following day).

14.3.2 Prepare vials

Place the roller in a fume hood.

Remove the screw-top lids of 36 vials.

Pipette 500ul of acetone into each vial (control vials).

Place the vials horizontally onto a roller.

Set the roller to spin at a moderate speed (~24 rpm).

Leave the vials rolling for 1 hour at room temperature (21°C).

Label each vial and re-attach screw-top lids.

Store the vials upright at 4°C in the dark (fridge) for at least 24 hours. Afterwards vials are ready for use. Continue to store at 4°C in the dark prior to use in the bioassays.

Repeat the steps 3.2.2 – 3.2.8 for the lowest concentration (0.041 ppm).

Repeat the steps 3.2.2 – 3.2.8 for the next concentration (0.204 ppm).

Repeat the steps 3.2.2 – 3.2.8 for the next concentration (1.02 ppm).

Repeat the steps 3.2.2 – 3.2.8 for the next concentration (5.1 ppm).

Repeat the steps 3.2.2 – 3.2.8 for the highest concentration (10.2 ppm).

15 Coated glass vials test – preparation of acetamiprid coated vials

SOP reference number: UJ-11

15.1 Objective

Preparation of acetamiprid coated glass vials for acute contact tests

15.2 Materials

15.2.1 Necessary materials/equipment

- Technical grade acetamiprid (available from Sigma)
- Technical-grade acetone
- Glass vials which are 5 cm high x 2 cm in diameter (having an internal glass surface area of 34.56 cm², suggested supplier is S Murray and Co, Holborn House, High St, Old Woking, Woking, GU22 9LB, UK:)
- Roller
- Fridge (4°C)
- Standard laboratory equipment

15.3 Procedures

15.3.1 Prepare solutions

Procedure to prepare 110.60, 55.30, 11.06, 2.21, 0.44 ppm acetamiprid solutions in acetone. These equate to 1.6, 0.8, 0.16, 0.032, 0.0064 µg ai/cm² (200%, 100%, 20%, 4%, 0.8% maximum field rate respectively) when a volume of 500 µl is used per vial.

If needed prepare the stock solution. To obtain stock solution (1000 ppm) add **10 mg** of technical acetamiprid to the flask and dissolve it in **10 mL** of acetone. Vortex the solution. Stock solution can be stored in the dark at 4°C.

Prepare the range of concentrations.

Add **5.53 mL** of stock solution (1000 ppm) to a volumetric flask (**50 cm³**) and fill it to volume with acetone to obtain 50 mL of 110.59 ppm solution. Vortex the solution.

Add **12.5 mL** of 110.60 ppm solution to volumetric flask (**25 cm³**) and fill it to volume with acetone to obtain 25 mL of 55.30 ppm solution. Vortex the solution.

Add **5 mL** of 55.30 ppm solution to volumetric flask (**25 cm³**) and fill it to volume with acetone to obtain 25 mL of 11.06 ppm solution. Vortex the solution.

Add **5 mL** of 11.06 ppm solution to volumetric flask (**25 cm³**) and fill it to volume with acetone to obtain 25 mL of 2.21 ppm solution. Vortex the solution.

Add **5 mL** of 2.21 ppm solution to volumetric flask (**25 cm³**) and fill it to volume with acetone to obtain 25 mL of 0.44 ppm solution. Vortex the solution.

Store the solutions in the dark at room temperature (if used the same day) or at 4°C (if used the following day).

15.3.2 Prepare vials

Place the roller in a fume hood.

Remove the screw-top lids of 36 vials.

Pipette 500 µL of acetone into each vial (control vials).

Place open vials horizontally onto a roller.

Set the roller to spin at a moderate speed (~24 rpm).

Leave the vials rolling for 1 hour at room temperature (ca. 21°C).

Label each vial, write 'ACT' on the label and re-attach screw-top lids add.

Store the vials upright at 4°C in the dark (fridge) for at least 24 hours. Afterwards vials are ready for use. Continue to store at 4°C in the dark prior to use in the bioassays.

Repeat the steps 3.2.2 – 3.2.8 for the lowest concentration (0.44 ppm).

Repeat the steps 3.2.2 – 3.2.8 for the next higher concentration (2.21 ppm).

Repeat the steps 3.2.2 – 3.2.8 for the next concentration (11.06 ppm).

Repeat the steps 3.2.2 – 3.2.8 for the next concentration (55.30 ppm).

Repeat the steps 3.2.2 – 3.2.8 for the highest concentration (110.6 ppm).

16 Coated glass vials test – preparation of chlorpyrifos coated vials

SOP reference number: UJ-12

16.1 Objective

Preparation of chlorpyrifos coated glass vials for acute contact tests

16.2 Materials

16.2.1 Necessary materials/equipment

- Technical grade chlorpyrifos (available from Sigma)
- Technical-grade acetone
- Glass vials which are 5 cm high x 2 cm in diameter (having an internal glass surface area of 34.56 cm², suggested supplier is S Murray and Co, Holborn House, High St, Old Woking, Woking, GU22 9LB, UK:)
- Roller
- Fridge (4°C)
- Standard laboratory equipment

16.3 Procedures

16.3.1 Prepare solutions

Procedure to prepare 7.96, 1.59, 0.318, 0.064, 0.013 ppm chlorpyrifos solutions in acetone. These equate to 0.152, 0.031, 0.006, 0.001, 0.0002 µg ai/cm² (4%, 0.8%, 0.16%, 0.032%, 0.0064%) field rate respectively) when a volume of 500 µL is used per vial.

If needed, prepare the stock solution. To obtain stock solution (1000 ppm) add **10 mg** of technical chlorpyrifos to the flask and dissolve it in **10 mL** of acetone. Vortex the solution. Stock solution can be stored in the dark at 4°C.

Prepare the range of concentrations.

Add **398 µL (0.398 mL)** of stock solution (1000 ppm) to volumetric flask (**50 cm³**) and fill it to volume with acetone to obtain 50 mL of 7.69 ppm solution. Vortex the solution.

Add **5 mL** of 7.69 ppm solution to volumetric flask (**25 cm³**) and fill it to volume with acetone to obtain 25 mL of 1.59 ppm solution. Vortex the solution.

Add **5 mL** of 1.59 ppm solution to volumetric flask (**25 cm³**) and fill it to volume with acetone to obtain 25 ml of 0.318 ppm solution. Vortex the solution.

Add **5 mL** of 0.318 ppm solution to volumetric flask (**25 cm³**) and fill it to volume with acetone to obtain 25 mL of 0.064 ppm solution. Vortex the solution.

Add **5 mL** of 0.064 ppm solution to volumetric flask (**25 cm³**) and fill it to volume with acetone to obtain 25 mL of 0.013 ppm solution. Vortex the solution.

Store the solutions in the dark at room temperature (if used the same day) or at 4°C (if used the following day).

16.3.2 Prepare vials

Place the roller in a fume hood.

Remove the screw-top lids of 36 vials.

Pipette 500 µL of acetone into each vial (control vials).

Place open vials horizontally onto a roller.

Set the roller to spin at a moderate speed (~24 rpm).

Leave the vials rolling for 1 hour at room temperature (21°C).

Label each vial, write 'CHP' on the label and re-attach screw-top lids add.

Store the vials upright at 4°C in the dark (fridge) for at least 24 hours. Afterwards vials are ready for use. Continue to store at 4°C in the dark prior to use in the bioassays.

Repeat the steps 3.2.2 – 3.2.8 for the lowest concentration (0.013 ppm).

Repeat the steps 3.2.2 – 3.2.8 for the next concentration (0.064 ppm).

Repeat the steps 3.2.2 – 3.2.8 for the next concentration (0.318 ppm).

Repeat the steps 3.2.2 – 3.2.8 for the next concentration (1.59 ppm).

Repeat the steps 3.2.2 – 3.2.8 for the highest concentration (7.69 ppm).